

HPV Study Initiation Package, including study protocol
Deliverable D4.1

11.2023 (Revised in March 2025)

DISCLAIMER

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Digital Executive Agency (HADEA) (‘EU executive agency’ or ‘granting authority’). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

While the information contained in the documents is believed to be accurate, the authors(s) or any other participant in the consortium make no warranty of any kind with regard to this material including, but not limited to the implied warranties of merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose.

Neither the Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees, or agents shall be responsible or liable in negligence or otherwise howsoever in respect of any inaccuracy or omission herein. Without derogating from the generality of the foregoing neither the Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be liable for any direct or indirect or consequential loss or damage caused by or arising from any information advice or inaccuracy or omission herein.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Project information	
Project title	Cancer Prevention at Work: Occupational health surveillance in the implementation of prevention of infection-related cancer.
Acronym	CPW
Project URL	www.cancerpreventionatwork.eu
EC Grant Agreement n.	101104716
Call	HORIZON-MISS-2022-CANCER-01 submitted for HORIZON-MISS-2022-CANCER-01
Call Topic	HORIZON-MISS-2022-CANCER-01-01 - Improving and upscaling primary prevention of cancer through implementation research
Type of Action	HORIZON-RIA
Project start/end date	01.05.2023 > 30.04.2027
Project duration	48 months
EU Project officer	[REDACTED]
Project coordinator	Paolo Boffetta (paolo.boffetta@unibo.it)
Project manager	[REDACTED]

Deliverable information	
Deliverable n.	D4.1
Work package n.	WP4
Task n.	4.2
Deliverable title	Human papilloma virus (HPV) Study Initiation Package including study protocol
Lead beneficiary	RAPH BB
Participants	UNIBO, RAPH BB, SDU, FDRH, ISP, UNITO, UKHD, RPA Prague, ZP, ASL TO
Main authors	For RAPH BB: Z. Klöslová, D. Mašlejová, E. Fabiánová, J. O. Béréšová
Contributors	All participants
Reviewed by	UNIBO, RAPH BB, SDU, FDRH, ISP, UNITO, UKHD, RPA Prague, ZP, ASL TO
E-mail Contact for queries	fabianova@vzbb.sk , kloslova@vzbb.sk , maslejova@vzbb.sk , beresova@vzbb.sk
Due date	30.11.2023
Document status	Final Version - revised
Document version	V4 – Revised in March 2025
Document type*	R
Dissemination level	Public

*Legend = R – Report // DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs // DEC – Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc. // DMP – Data management plan // OTHER – Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

	The CPW's Consortium; Name of the Entity	Acronym	Role	Country	ORG Type
1	Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna	UNIBO	C	IT	RTD
2	National Institute of Public Health	INSP	B	RO	PHI
3	Romanian Society for Occupational Medicine	SRMM	B	RO	SME
4	Clinic Hospital Colentina, Bucharest	Col Hosp	B	RO	Hosp
5	Timisoara Municipal Emergency Clinical Hospital	SCMUT	B	RO	Hosp
6	Regional Authority of Public Health Banská Bystrica	RAPH BB	B	SK	PHI
7	University of Southern Denmark	SDU	B	DK	RTD
8	WEDO Project Intelligence Made Easy SI	WeDo	B	ES	SME
9	F.D. Roosevelt University General Hospital of Banská Bystrica	FDRH	B	SK	Hosp
10	Fundacion para la investigacion y la innovacion biosanitaria del Principado de Asturias	FINBA	B	ES	NGO
11	Intesa Sanpaolo SPA	ISP	B	IT	LC
12	Università di Torino	UNITO	B	IT	RTD
14	Heidelberg University Hospital	UKHD	B	DE	RTD
15	RPA Europe Prague s.r.o.	RPA Prague	B	CZ	SME
16	Regione Emilia Romagna	RER	B	IT	PHI
17	Zeleziarne Podbrezova a.s.	ZP	B	SK	SME
18	ASL Città di Torino	ASL TO	B	IT	PHI
19	Health Service of the Principality of Asturias	SESPA	AP	ES	PHI

***Legend** = Role in the Project: **C** – Coordinator // **B** – Beneficiary // **AP** – Associated Partner // Organization Type: **RTD** – Research and Technological Development// **PHI** – Public Health Institution // **Hosp** – Hospital // **SME** – Small and medium-sized enterprises. // **LC** – Large Company // **NGO** – Non-Governmental Org.

	Work Packages Name	WP Leader
1	WP1 Coordination and Management	UNIBO
2	WP2 Gastric Cancer Prevention Through Helicobacter Pylori Screening and Treatment	FINBA
3	WP3 Liver Cancer Prevention Through HCV Screening and Treatment	INSP
4	WP4 Prevention of Cancers Associated with HPV Infection	RAPH BB
5	WP5 Behavioural and Sociocultural Assessment	SDU
6	WP6 Cost Effectiveness Analysis	RPA Prague
7	WP7 Dissemination, Outreach and Exploitation	WEDO

WP4 Working Group Composition					
	Entity	Acronym	Country	Name	e-mail
1	Alma Mater Studiorum University of Bologna	UNIBO			
2	National Institute of Public Health	INSP			
3	Regional Authority of Public Health Banská Bystrica	RAPH BB			
6	University of Southern Denmark	SDU			
7	WEDO Project Intelligence Made Easy	WeDo			
8	F.D. Roosevelt University General Hospital of Banská Bystrica	FDRH			
9	Intesa Sanpaolo SPA	ISP			
10	Università di Torino	UNITO			
11	Heidelberg University Hospital	UKHD			
12	RPA Europe Prague s.r.o.	RPA Prague			
13	Zeleziarne Podbrezova a.s.	ZP			
14	ASL Città di Torino	ASL TO			

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

This deliverable is an open access report, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s). The contributing partners own right on their contents, following the project grant agreement (101104716).

How to quote this document

Pilot study protocol for the HPV intervention in occupational health settings (CPW D4.1)

Table of Contents

1	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
2	SYNOPSIS	9
3	LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS	10
4	LIST OF FIGURES	10
5	LIST OF TABLES	10
6	INTRODUCTION	11
6.1	PROJECT INTRODUCTION.....	11
6.2	OBJECTIVES OF WP4 AND TASKS.....	11
6.3	CONTENTS OF THE DELIVERABLE D 4.1	12
7	BACKGROUND	12
7.1	STUDY RATIONALE	12
7.2	EXPECTED IMPACT	12
7.3	STUDY DESIGN	12
7.4	STUDY IMPLEMENTATION CENTRES DESCRIPTION	13
7.5	COMMUNICATION AND TRAINING ACTIVITIES	13
7.6	DATA SHARING	13
7.7	ETHICS	13
8	STUDY POPULATION AND ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA	14
9	ENROLLMENT AND DATA COLLECTION	14
9.1	PARTICIPANT ENROLMENT, COLLECTION OF DATA, TIMELINE, SAMPLE SIZE JUSTIFICATION	14
9.2	VACCINATION ALGORITHM	15
9.3	RECOMMENDATION ON HPV VACCINATION:.....	16
9.4	FOLLOW-UP OF SUBJECTS REGARDING THEIR DECISION ABOUT HPV VACCINATION.....	17
9.5	REIMBURSEMENT PROCEDURES AND RULES	17
10	COLLECTION OF SPECIMENS, STORAGE, PREPARATION AND TESTING PROCEDURE	17
11	ARCHIVES AND COMPUTERIZED DATA	18
12	OVERALL ENROLLMENT FLOWCHART	18
13	OCCUPATIONAL HEALTHCARE AS A CONTEXT OF IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGIES AND IMPLEMENTATION OUTCOMES	18
13.1	BACKGROUND	18
13.2	PROPOSED QUESTIONNAIRE FOR HEALTHCARE PROVIDERS AT THE BEGINNING AND END OF THE CPW SCREENING PROCEDURES	19
14	ANNEXES	20
14.1	ANNEX 1 INFORMED CONSENT TEMPLATE	20
14.2	ANNEX 2 BASELINE QUESTIONNAIRE	22
	PART 1: GENERAL INFORMATION	23
	PART 2: MEDICAL HISTORY	25
	PART 3: FAMILY MEDICAL HISTORY	27
	PART 5: BODY SIZE	28
	PART 6: DIET	28

7.1 Do YOU THINK HPV CAN CAUSE DIFFERENT TYPES OF CANCER? __ 	28
7.2 Do YOU THINK HPV CAN CAUSE CANCER OF THE CERVIX UTERI? __ 	28
7.3 Do YOU THINK HPV CAN CAUSE CANCER OF VAGINA, VULVA (FEMALE GENITALS)? __ 	29
7.4 Do YOU THINK HPV CAN CAUSE PENILE CANCER? __ 	29
7.5 Do YOU THINK HPV CAN CAUSE CANCER IN ANAL AND RECTAL AREA? __ 	29
7.6 Do YOU THINK HPV CAN CAUSE CANCER IN THE BACK OF THE THROAT, INCLUDING THE BASE OF THE TONGUE, TONSILS, PHARYNX AND LARYNX? __ 	29
7.7 Do YOU THINK THAT SOME TYPES OF HPV CAUSE GENITAL WARTS? __ 	29
7.8 Do YOU THINK THAT HPV INFECTION IS A SEXUALLY TRANSMITTED DISEASE? __ 	29
7.9 Do YOU THINK HPV CAN INFECT A PERSON WITHOUT VISIBLE SYMPTOMS? __ 	29
7.10 Do YOU THINK HPV INFECTIONS ARE RARE? __ 	29
7.11 Do YOU THINK THAT SOME CASES OF CERVICAL CANCER ARE NOT CAUSED BY HPV INFECTION? __ 	29
7.12 Do YOU THINK BOTH MEN AND WOMEN CAN BE INFECTED WITH HPV? __ 	29
7.13 Do YOU THINK THAT ONLY WOMEN CAN BE INFECTED WITH HPV? __ 	29
7.14 Do YOU THINK THAT SOME HPV INFECTIONS RESOLVE SPONTANEOUSLY? __ 	29
7.15 Do YOU THINK THAT YOU, YOUR PARTNER OR CHILDREN MAY BE EXPOSED TO THE RISK OF HPV INFECTION NOW OR IN THE FUTURE? __ 	29
7.16 Do YOU KNOW THAT IN COUNTRIES WITH ESTABLISHED HPV VACCINATION PROGRAMS THERE WAS A SIGNIFICANT DECREASE IN CERVICAL CANCER INCIDENCE (DROPPED BY AROUND 90 %)? __ 	29
PART 8: FEMALE QUESTIONNAIRE	29
8.1 Do YOU PARTICIPATE IN PREVENTIVE GYNAECOLOGICAL CHECK-UPS? __ 	29
<i>If yes:</i>	29
8.1.1 <i>If yes, in what frequency were they? __ </i>	29
8.1.2 <i>In which year was your last check-up?.....</i>	29
8.2 HAVE YOU EVER BEEN SCREENED /TESTED FOR HPV INFECTION OR CERVICAL TISSUE CHANGES? __ 	29
<i>If yes:</i>	30
8.2.1 <i>What type of test was it? __ </i>	30
8.2.2 <i>What was the result? __ </i>	30
8.2.3 <i>In case of positive result, have you got medical treatment of the uterine cervix? __ </i>	30
PART 9: KNOWLEDGE ABOUT VACCINATION AGAINST HPV	30
9.3 Do YOU KNOW THAT FULLY REIMBURSED VACCINES (VACCINATION) AGAINST HPV ARE INTENDED FOR CHILDREN UP TO 15 YEARS OF AGE? __ 	30
9.4 Do YOU THINK HPV VACCINES WORK BETTER IF GIVEN BEFORE AGE 15? __ 	30
9.5 Do YOU THINK HPV VACCINES CAN ALSO BE ADMINISTERED TO ADULTS UP TO 45 YEARS OF AGE? __ 	30
9.6 Do YOU THINK HPV VACCINES PROTECT AGAINST ALL TYPES OF HPV? __ 	30
9.7 HAVE YOU BEEN VACCINATED AGAINST HPV INFECTION? __ 	30
9.8 HAS YOUR DOCTOR OFFERED YOU THE OPPORTUNITY TO BE VACCINATED AGAINST HPV? __ 	30
<i>IF YES:</i>	30
9.8.1 <i>WHICH SPECIALITY DOCTOR? __ </i>	30
9.9 Do YOU WANT TO BE VACCINATED AGAINST HPV WITHIN THE FRAMEWORK OF THIS PROJECT? __ 	30
9.10 HAS YOUR PARTNER OR CHILDREN ALREADY BEEN VACCINATED AGAINST HPV? __ 	30
<i>If yes: 9.10.1 Who has been vaccinated?.....</i>	30
9.11 Do YOU WANT TO TAKE THE OPPORTUNITY TO VACCINATE YOUR FAMILY MEMBER (PARTNER, CHILDREN) AGAINST HPV WITHIN THE FRAMEWORK OF THIS PROJECT? __ 	30
PART 10: REASONS FOR REFUSAL OF HPV VACCINATION (MULTIPLE ANSWERS POSSIBLE)	31
10.1 WHAT ARE YOUR REASONS FOR REFUSING THE HPV VACCINATION? (POSSIBILITY OF MULTIPLE ANSWERS)	31
PART 11: HPV VACCINE ADMINISTRATION	31
11.1 WHERE DO YOU WANT TO GET VACCINATED AGAINST HPV? __ 	31
11.2 WHERE DO YOU PLAN TO VACCINATE YOUR FAMILY MEMBER(S) AGAINST HPV? (CONNECTED TO ANSWER TO QUESTION 9.11.1) 31	31
14.3 ANNEX 3 SELF-ADMINISTRATED BASELINE QUESTIONNAIRE	32
1.4 PLEASE MARK YOUR ANSWER ON THE SCALE WHICH APPLIES TO YOU.	33
1.4.2 TO WHAT EXTENT DO YOU FEEL RESPONSIBLE FOR YOUR HEALTH?	33

1.6 Do YOU HAVE SAVINGS/FINANCIAL FUNDS THAT (IN CASE OF LOSING YOUR INCOME) COULD COVER YOUR EXPENSES FOR AT LEAST 3 SUBSEQUENT MONTHS? __ (0=NO; 1=YES)	33
1.7 Do YOU HAVE A GROUP OF CLOSE FRIENDS YOU FEEL YOU BELONG TO? __ (0=NO; 1=YES).....	33
1.7.1 How often do you meet your close friends? __ 	33
1.8.1 __ READING __ SPEAKING __ WRITING	33
1.8.2 __ READING __ SPEAKING __ WRITING	33
1.8.3 __ READING __ SPEAKING __ WRITING	33
14.4 ANNEX 4 PROTOCOL TO ASSESS WORKER’S SELF-PERCEIVED HEALTH CAPITAL	40
14.5 ANNEX 5 SUBJECT LOG-SHEET.....	42
14.6 ANNEX 6 FOLLOW-UP QUESTIONNAIRE.....	43
14.7 ANNEX 7 QUESTIONNAIRE FOR OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH PROVIDERS - BASELINE	47
14.8 ANNEX 8 QUESTIONNAIRE FOR OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH PROVIDERS – FOLLOW-UP	50
15 FIGURES.....	56
16 TABLES	57
17 UPDATES FOLLOWING THE 1ST PROJECT TECHNICAL REVIEW	58

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is Deliverable 4.1 (“HPV Study Initiation Package, including study protocol”) of the CANCER PREVENTION AT WORK project. It is issued under the responsibility of The Regional Authority of Public Health, Banská Bystrica, Slovakia (RAPH BB) with the contribution of a working group comprising principal investigators and team members from the implementation centers in Slovakia, Italy, and principal investigators from partners in Denmark, Germany, Czech Republic and Spain.

The CPW intervention for HPV prevention by promoting vaccination against HPV will be conducted on three different occupational cohorts of minimum 1000 participants (health care workers, finance workers, and metal workers including their family members) in the context of routine medical surveillance carried out in occupational health settings.

Occupation health surveillance is mandatory in all European countries: although the mechanisms of its implementation vary between the countries, these programs are in general aimed at diagnosing and preventing work-related diseases. Prevention of occupational cancers has therefore been a component of occupational health surveillance.

In recent years, however, there has been a movement towards including in occupational health surveillance aspects of health promotion which are not occupational in a strict sense. A person as a biopsychosocial unit should be informed about potential health risks and should be protected against them comprehensively.

This approach stems from several considerations:

- i. the contact between the worker and the health professional in charge of the surveillance can be seen as a privileged opportunity for health promotion in general;
- ii. through the worker, the health promotion initiative may reach other groups of the population;
- iii. because of the periodic nature of the visits entailed by the occupational health surveillance, it is possible to efficiently implement follow-up mechanisms. The conceptual framework of the proposed research is based on the incorporation into on-going occupational surveillance schemes of primary prevention program against HPV infection.

Therefore, the D4.1 consists in a protocol of a multicenter, multinational interventional pilot study aimed at building several types of working cohorts in which to assess the feasibility of HPV prevention in the form of anti-HPV vaccination. The results will be monitored in a follow-up stage.

The protocol, which has been discussed and agreed with all the WP4 partners, will be submitted for local ethical evaluation. Each partner in its own country will undergo necessary procedures for obtaining the approval by local Ethics Committee.

The intended audience of this deliverable consists of members of the CPW consortium and the European Commission.

2 SYNOPSIS

WP4 Protocol working group	E. Fabiánová, Z. Klöslová, J. Oravec Béréšová, Z. Klócová Adamčáková, D. Mašlejová, J. Beláková, P. Boffetta, A. Cataneo, S. Mellone, D. Mates, A. Schneider-Kamp, T. Rageliene, A. Honrado, R. Vilček, M. Jendrušáková, E. Púchyová, V. Pohančaniková, L. Mojžišová, Z. Bečková, V. Ďurajová, E. Gorra, M. Venturini, E. Stocco, A. Godono, V. De Pasquale, M. Wensing, D. Vencovsky, E. Murínová, E. Kapustíková, M. Kočtúchová Blažinová, L. Latináková, Ľ. Kamenská, B. Korbelová, R. Gili.
Project Coordinator	Paolo Boffetta, UNIBO
Study rationale	Pilot intervention, targeted to the prevention of HPV infection-related cancers, which will be conducted within the framework of existing occupational health surveillance program in three centres, on four different workers groups. The intervention will follow the World health Organisation (WHO) guidelines focusing mainly on HPV vaccination. After 6 months, a follow-up will be conducted to record attitudes and decisions of the respondents and their family members (FMs) towards HPV vaccination.
Study design	Multicentre, prospective, interventional (HPV vaccination recommendation and follow-up of decisions towards HPV vaccination.)
Study population	Health care workers (HCW), metal workers, finance institution workers and their FMs.
Inclusion criteria	All workers participating in preventive medical examinations at work providing informed consent to participate as respondents. For HPV vaccination: all workers participating in the preventive medical check-up under the age of 45 and their FMs suitable for vaccination.
Exclusion criteria	Unable to consent. For HPV vaccination: pregnancy.
Contraindicated or Not Recommended	Severe allergic reaction (e.g., anaphylaxis) after a previous dose or to a vaccine component
Precautions	Moderate or severe acute illness with or without fever
Timeline	24 months: enrolment, 12 months: follow-up
Partners involved	UNIBO, RAPH BB, SDU, FDRH, ISP, UNITO, UKHD, ZP, ASL TO

3 LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Description
CPW	Cancer Prevention at Work project
DMP	Data management plan
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
GP	General practitioner
HPV	Human Papilloma Virus
ID	Identification number
OH	Occupational health
WP	Work Package
EMA	European Medical Agency

4 LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Overall flow-chart of the HPV study

5 LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Description of the implementation centres for HPV

Table 2: Prevention and health promotion initiatives in the implementation centres

Table 3: Resources dedicated to the project in the implementation centres

6 INTRODUCTION

6.1 Project introduction

Chronic infections represent a major cause of human cancer: on a global scale, they are responsible for an estimated 13% of human cancers. *Helicobacter pylori* (Hp), Hepatitis C virus (HCV), and Human Papilloma Virus (HPV) are responsible together for 75% of these cases, or 10% of total cancer burden¹. Occupational health surveillance is mandatory in all European countries: although the mechanisms of its implementation vary between the countries, these programs are in general aimed at diagnosing and preventing work-related diseases. Prevention of occupational cancers has therefore been a component of Occupational health (OH) surveillance. In recent years, however, there has been a movement towards including in occupational health surveillance aspects of health promotion which are not occupational in a strict sense. This approach stems from several considerations: (i) the contact between the worker and the health professional in charge of the surveillance can be seen as a privileged opportunity for health promotion in general; (ii) through the worker, the health promotion initiative may reach other groups of the population; (iii) because of the periodic nature of the visits entailed by the occupational health surveillance, it is possible to efficiently implement follow-up mechanisms. The conceptual framework of the proposed research is based on the incorporation into preventive medical check-ups at work of primary prevention programs against Hp, HCV and HPV infections. The overarching objectives of the proposed research are: - to conduct a series of pilot projects aimed at assessing the effectiveness (including cost-effectiveness) of incorporating primary prevention interventions against Hp, HCV and HPV into existing occupational surveillance systems in high-risk populations, including its impact beyond the workers directly involved in the pilot projects; - to identify barriers and bottlenecks for the implementation of such interventions. This action is part of the Cancer Mission cluster of projects on 'Prevention and early detection'.

6.2 Objectives of WP4 and tasks

The overarching objective of WP4 is the implementation of HPV Vaccination as primary prevention of HPV infection and its complications including cervical, anal, vulvar, vaginal, penile, and oropharyngeal cancer within occupational health surveillance programs.

HPV infection is associated with 5 % of all cancers in the world. Cervical cancer is the fourth most common cancer among women globally, with an estimated 604 000 new cases and 342 000 deaths in 2020. The highest incidence and death rates are in developing countries with low income and socioeconomic level. In the EU, cervical cancer is the second most common cancer after breast cancer to affect women aged 15 – 44. Each year, there are around 33 000 cases of cervical cancer in the EU, and 15 000 deaths. Other cancers caused by HPV include other anogenital cancers as well as oropharyngeal cancer.

Comprehensive cervical cancer control includes, as primary prevention, vaccination against HPV. Three vaccines are currently licensed in the EU. They are safe and effective in preventing infections with HPV infections, high grade precancerous lesions and invasive cancer. HPV vaccines work best if administered prior to exposure to HPV.

The Specific Objectives of WP4 include:

- O4.1 To design the protocol for HPV vaccination of workers involved in occupational health surveillance, including follow-up and promotion of HPV vaccination of eligible family members (FMs) of workers;
- O4.2 To implement the pilot project on HPV vaccination in participating centres;
- O4.3 To analyse the data collected within the pilot project on determinants of vaccination;
- O4.4 Based on the results of the pilot project, to develop plans for large-scale implementation of HPV prevention within occupational health surveillance systems.

¹ De Martel C., Georges D., Bray F., Ferlay J., Clifford G.M. Global burden of cancer attributable to infections in 2018: a worldwide incidence analysis. *Lancet Glob Health.* 2020;8: e180-e190.

O4.5 To engage the national stakeholders in the implementation and/or adaptation of country tailored preventive interventions for HPV infection within existing occupational health surveillance programs.

The objectives of WP4 will be reached by completing the following tasks:

Task 4.1. Identification and evaluation of current national/regional programs for prevention of HPV-related cancers.

Task 4.2. Design of a protocol for a pilot study on implementation of HPV vaccination of eligible workers involved in occupational health surveillance, and their household members.

Task 4.3. Implementation and coordination of the pilot project on HPV vaccination in selected centres participating in CPW.

Task 4.4. Analysis of data collected within the pilot projects on HPV prevention on determinants of effectiveness of intervention.

Task 4.5. Development of plans for large-scale implementation of prevention of HPV-related cancers within occupational health surveillance systems.

Task 4.6. Identification of the best strategies to increase the adherence of European populations to the program of vaccination against HPV.

6.3 Contents of the deliverable D 4.1

Deliverable 4.1 is a public report and contains the protocol developed by the WP4 working group to prevent HPV-related cancer through promotion of HPV vaccination. The protocol is designed in accordance with the specifications of task 4.2.

7 BACKGROUND

7.1 Study rationale

The feasibility of incorporating primary prevention intervention for HPV into existing occupational surveillance systems, in occupational groups with various risk level, needs to be explored. Cost-effectiveness, barriers and facilitators, acceptance and compliance, beyond the group of workers directly involved will be evaluate in comparison with other community based preventive interventions.

7.2 Expected impact

Available literature suggests that HPV interventions have the potential to be cost-effective, albeit not in all interventions. Cost-effectiveness ratios in the literature vary and depend on a number of factors, such as the targeting of the intervention (high risk vs low risk group). There is thus a need to improve our understanding of the impact that the design of such interventions (especially in the European context) and structural conditions can have on cost-effectiveness. In addition, there is a significant need to improve the evidence base for public health interventions implemented within the framework of OH surveillance. This is particularly significant given the potential for occupational health surveillance to be a comparatively more cost-effective tool for the relevant interventions. If the results of the pilot studies will be successful and cost-effective, the research group, together with relevant stakeholders, will be able to provide guidance and recommendations for large-scale implementation of the intervention

7.3 Study design

The scheme for the HPV intervention is shown in Figure 1. The study will be designed as an intervention study with cross-sectional surveys for evaluation. The survey will be carried out before intervention activities and three months after the intervention in the same participant. The intervention will target workers and their household members. Selected multicentre groups of recipients (employees) from larger entities will be established. The emphasis will be on individual preventive medical advice and support. During the routine preventive medical examinations at work all eligible workers will be informed by explanatory letter and counselled about the benefits of the intervention. Respondents and their household members (targeted age groups and sex(es)) will also be approached and invited for HPV vaccination. Depending on the countries/regional health care system, a clinical pathway is designed in collaboration with stakeholders. The participants will be followed up to gather information on their attitude and decision regarding HPV

vaccination. Occupational physicians and OH staff will be surveyed regarding acceptance and adoption of the planned interventions. OH teams will also receive additional training and support regarding behavioural counselling regarding screening and vaccination for HPV. Participants will be asked to fill in the entry questionnaire in order to assess their self- and household members' awareness and attitude regarding HPV-related cancer and preventive aspects of HPV vaccination. For those refusing the participation, a minimum set of data will be collected including the reason for non-participation. Six months after the intervention, a short follow-up questionnaire will be completed to obtain information about their final attitudes towards HPV vaccination and consequent behavioural changes. As concerns the HPV vaccination, the rules of national HPV vaccination programmes will be followed

7.4 Study implementation centres description

The study is implemented as a pilot intervention in different countries and occupational settings and will target various occupational group with various risk levels. A brief description of the implementation centres is presented in Table 1.

Given these multi-faceted aspects of the implementation centres, it is important that the study protocol takes into account the local specificities and allows a certain amount of flexibility in its implementation.

7.5 Communication and training activities

In order to enhance the evidence-based knowledge of key groups (companies' managers, workers) on the HPV-related cancer, various educational, informative materials (e.g., booklets, leaflets, posters), tailored to specific audience, will be prepared at the project level and will be translated in the local languages and disseminated in the implementation centres, prior to the start of the recruitment.

All OH teams will be trained locally on the standard procedures of the HPV intervention protocol.

Another key component of the HPV intervention will aim at additional training of the OH teams with a focus on personal communication skills, guidance and counselling services. These activities will be organized at project level and locally. The emphasis will be on enhancement of worker motivation to participate in the study and how to offer counselling also to their FMs.

7.6 Data sharing

Data generated at different stages of the pilot study will be managed, organized and released using procedures and infrastructure that are being developed in the DMP, describing the principles, standards, methods process and policies regarding the storage, curation, and dissemination of the data collected in CPW under FAIR principles. The data management at local level is under the responsibility of the specific partner who generated the data.

The data sharing procedures, including measures to guarantee privacy and data protection, are subject to a joint data controller agreement between all the research teams involved in the project.

7.7 Ethics

The intervention must be carried out in line with the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles. Patient's informed consent template, comprising the minimum items required by the intervention, has been developed. Implementation centres can adapt it or use local variant, provided that all minimum requirements are included. Questionnaires and forms to collect data from the participant have been developed by a working group comprising the PIs and other specialists from each implementation centre, and are annexed to this protocol. Each centre is responsible with the translation/adaptation of these documents to the local languages and context. A pilot test on a subset subject of the intended population to validate the questionnaires will take place in each centre/country.

The intervention requires appropriate local ethical approval. Once ethical and administrative authorizations are in place, the intervention can start in the implementation centre.

8 STUDY POPULATION AND ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

All workers participating in the preventive medical check-ups at work will be approached before or during the routine OH medical examination and will be invited to take part in the CPW project as respondents. Informative materials explaining the purpose of the study will be distributed at workplace to facilitate the understanding of the study objectives and acceptance of the study procedures. During the OH medical check-up, the OH doctor will inform each worker about the CPW (WP4) project background and provide more details about HPV-related cancer prevention through vaccination. It will be stressed that vaccination against HPV is optimally carried out before the first sexual experience at the age of 15, but it is also advisable to be vaccinated later, up to the age of 45. It means that vaccination within the project can be offered to the CPW study respondents below 45 or the vaccination can be given to their first-degree FMs (i.e., partner or children).

The timeline of the OH medical check-ups will depend on the local practice in each implementation.

Minimum eligibility criteria for index subjects:

- all workers under OH surveillance;
- for HPV vaccination: workers under OH surveillance in the age under 45 years

Exclusion criteria for participation for the study:

- subjects are excluded if they have any condition that could interfere with their ability to provide informed consent such as dementia or severe cognitive impairment

Exclusion criteria for HPV vaccination:

- pregnancy

Contraindications and precautions for HPV vaccination:

- severe allergic reaction (e.g., anaphylaxis) after a previous dose or to a vaccine component;
- moderate or severe acute illness with or without fever.

9 ENROLLMENT AND DATA COLLECTION

Where: Participating OH services

Who: OH staff and the local research team

What: Consent form, clinical, demographical, lifestyle and outcome data

How: Interview with the respondent using standard questionnaire, self-administrated questionnaire, data extracted from OH medical records, etc.

The purpose of this chapter is to outline standardized procedures for subjects' recruitment and to eliminate major discrepancies between centres. All information is collected from workers invited to participate in the project and that have given their specific consent to participate in the HPV intervention, or their general consent to participate to parallel interventions in CPW, when the consent provided is consistent with them.

9.1 Participant enrolment, collection of data, timeline, sample size justification

Prospective recruitment of all subjects will take place according to the following strategy:

- The subject is identified before or during the OH regular visit and its eligibility to the study is confirmed;
- The subject is informed of the study (scope, objective, procedures, results, etc.) and if she/he agree to participate, they are requested to complete and sign the informed consent form (Annex 1)
- A baseline questionnaire (Annex 2) is administered by a trained interviewer from the occupational health staff. A self-administrated questionnaire (Annex 3) is given to each participant to be completed in a pseudo-anonymized form. These questionnaires are completed on the implementation site, ensuring privacy of respondent and are collected in special closed boxes/envelope.
- A special questionnaire is dedicated to collect participant subconscious subjective perception of his/her health capital resources, using the projective technique. The details of the protocol for the projective technique to assess worker's self-perceived health capital are presented in Annex 4.

- All the questionnaires will be translated/adapted to the native language of the respondents and tested/validated accordingly.
- The study staff explains the content and assists the respondent if questions or queries arise.

Timeline

We envisage the official start of the recruitment will be May 2024. According to the project timeline, recruitment is anticipated to conclude by M36. The Grant Agreement specifies that the completion of recruitment for pilot studies is scheduled for M36, with follow-up activities extending beyond this period and estimated up to months 37–42 of the project. In some recruitment centres, particularly those delivering more than one intervention, the enrolment period may be extended until the full planned timeframe is completed.

Sample size justification

A total of 1,000 workers will be included in each center. This sample size will be sufficient to provide evidence of effectiveness of the intervention, which would increase the vaccination rate from 39.2% (the average rate of vaccination in the target population in Europe) to 43.5% (11% difference). These estimates will be compared with actual proportions of participation, adherence, and completion of the intervention measured during the progress of the project.

9.2 Vaccination algorithm

The vaccination against HPV within the project will be offered to the CPW study respondents below 45 and their first-degree FMs. For partner of the respondents the same “age rule for vaccination” applies. For children it is recommended to be vaccinated before the age of 15. In the EU the anti HPV vaccination can be started at the age of 9, but this is country-specific. In the CPW study the national rules for anti HPV vaccination have to be followed.

Within the frame of the CPW project the vaccination against HPV will be performed in the pilot implementation centres in the Slovak Republic and in Italy. In Slovakia the vaccination campaign started in 2008.

From 1 May 2022, Slovakia has joined other countries of the European Union and the nine-valent HPV vaccine Gardasil 9 became fully covered in Slovakia. This move has significantly increased the vaccination coverage of children aged 12 years who have the vaccine fully covered by public health insurance.

In Italy, the vaccination campaign started irregularly in 2007, with pre-adolescent girls as the primary target. Later, other cohorts were introduced such as 12-year-old boys, additional cohorts of >25-year-old women, women who already underwent cervical surgery and other subjects entitled to free vaccination.²

In Italy, the respondents will be informed of the possibility of being vaccinated in a vaccination hub by ASL Città di Torino. They will be offered a range of dates and an email address (or a platform) to book the vaccination appointment. Through email the participants will be able to inquire about the vaccination of family members.

In the Slovak Republic, the respondent can decide to undergo HPV vaccination immediately during the preventive medical examination or later. Likewise, a decision can be made in a short time to vaccinate FMs.

Each centre will have a designated contact point and communication strategy to effectively process the vaccination request. After the positive decision on vaccination, the parts about the vaccine are added to the basic questionnaire of the respondent and to the documentation of the vaccination process.

² Gabutti G, d'Anchera E, De Motoli F, Savio M, Stefanati A. Human Papilloma Virus Vaccination: Focus on the Italian Situation. *Vaccines* (Basel). 2021 Nov 23;9(12):1374. doi: 10.3390/vaccines9121374. PMID: 34960120; PMCID: PMC8708418.

Consequently, the respondent will receive details of the next steps of vaccination including the communication letter for chosen vaccinating doctor.

Vaccination against HPV must be recorded by the vaccinating doctor (centre). The same rule applies for a reimbursement of the costs of the vaccination from project funds.

9.3 Recommendation on HPV vaccination:

Since 2006, vaccines have been available to prevent HPV infection and HPV-associated illness. Three products are currently licensed in the European Union (EU)³:

- Cervarix - Bivalent vaccine against two types of HPV 16 and 18 (GlaxoSmithKline Biologicals, Rixensart, Belgium);
- Gardasil - Quadrivalent vaccine against four types of HPV 6, 11, 16, 18 (MSD VACCINS, Lyon, France).
- Gardasil 9- Nine-valent vaccine against nine types of HPV: 6, 11, 16, 18, 31, 33, 45, 52 and 58 (MSD VACCINS).

These vaccines can be administered to both males and females. All three vaccines include highly purified virus-like particles (VLPs) of the major HPV L1 protein and provide protection from HPV 16 and 18 genotypes associated with more than 90% of pre-cancerous lesions diagnosed in Europe. HPV vaccines are formulated to induce humoral immune responses, are effective, well tolerate and safe (VLPs are unable to infect cells, reproduce or cause disease in vaccinated subjects).

Accordingly, to the age, the vaccination schedule provides for the administration of two doses at 0 and 6 months for subjects up to 13 or 14 years or the administration of three doses at the time 0, 1–2 and 6 months for subjects >14 years of age. The three-dose schedule is recommended even if the interval between the first two doses was less than five months or if the subject is suffering from immunosuppression.

All three licensed vaccines have proven their safety in clinical trials submitted at the time of their approval and are currently undergoing post-marketing monitoring by the EMA and other European national drug agencies confirming their safety⁴.

Human papillomavirus vaccination by Gardasil 9:

Gardasil 9 helps protect individuals ages 9 to 45 against the following diseases caused by 9 types of HPV: cervical, vaginal, and vulvar cancers in females, anal cancer, certain head and neck cancers, such as throat and back of mouth cancers and genital warts in both males and females.

Gardasil 9 may not fully protect everyone, nor will it protect against diseases caused by other HPV types or against diseases not caused by HPV. Gardasil 9 does not prevent all types of cervical, vulvar, vaginal, anal or head and neck cancers. Vaccination does not remove the need for recommended screenings for these cancers, and it is important for girls to get routine cervical cancer screenings later in life and for women to continue routine cervical cancer screenings. Gardasil 9 does not treat cancer or genital warts.

Gardasil 9 is a shot that is usually given in the arm muscle. Gardasil 9 may be given as 2 or 3 shots.

For persons 9 through 14 years of age, Gardasil 9 can be given using a 2-dose or 3-dose schedule. For the 2-dose schedule, the second shot should be given 6–12 months after the first shot. If the second shot is given less than 5 months after the first shot, a third shot should be given at least 4 months after

³ European Medical Agency: Human papillomavirus vaccines - Cervarix, Gardasil, Gardasil 9, Silgard, Available at: <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/referrals/human-papillomavirus-vaccines-cervarix-gardasil-gardasil-9-silgard>

⁴ European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control. Guidance on HPV Vaccination in EU Countries: Focus on Boys, People Living with HIV and 9-Valent HPV Vaccine Introduction, 2020. ECDC; Stockholm, Sweden.2020.

the second shot. For the 3-dose schedule, the second shot should be given 2 months after the first shot and the third shot should be given 6 months after the first shot.

For persons 15 through 45 years of age, Gardasil 9 is given using a 3-dose schedule; the second shot should be given 2 months after the first shot and the third shot should be given 6 months after the first shot.

Side effects of HPV vaccination

The safety and efficacy of vaccines have been demonstrated at a very high level. As with all drugs, side effects can occur. Most commonly, however, redness, itching and swelling at the site of administration. Headache, muscle pain and fatigue may occur. Transient discomfort of the digestive system such as nausea, vomiting, diarrhea or abdominal pain has also been described. Very rarely, severe (anaphylactic) allergic reactions might occur after vaccination. People with severe allergies to any component of a vaccine should not receive that vaccine.

9.4 Follow-up of subjects regarding their decision about HPV vaccination

The subjects are followed after six months to collect data on their attitude towards HPV vaccination. The information regarding respondents' and their family members' decisions (positive/negative) towards HPV vaccination (including next dose(s) of HPV vaccine) will be collected using a follow-up questionnaire completed by the respondent (employ of the implementation centre). (Annex 6).

9.5 Reimbursement procedures and rules

As of May 1, 2022, the Slovak Republic has joined other EU countries with full reimbursement of the nonvalent vaccine. This step was expected to rapidly increase vaccination coverage rates in this core cohort providing better protection for the youth. Currently, a bivalent vaccine and a nonvalent vaccine are available free of charge between the 12th and 13th birthday of the child. The first dose can be given at any time of age 12 years old. The second dose is also fully reimbursed and should be administered between 5 and 13 months after the first dose. The HPV vaccine is administered by paediatricians. HPV vaccination in other age groups (13+ years) is not fully reimbursed from public health insurance and these groups have to pay for it in pharmacies. Health insurance companies, however, provide some level of payback within their benefit programs for age groups 13 – 17.⁵ From December 1, 2023, the vaccine will be fully reimbursed also for 13- 14 years old.

So, to get the reimbursement from the CPW project funds, each study participant who is eligible for HPV vaccination (including his/her first degree FMs) and does not fulfil criteria mentioned above, needs:

- to provide proof of being vaccinated against HPV. The following information from the vaccinating doctor (centre) is required: name of the vaccine, batch number, date of administration, name of vaccinator, any data on adverse effects of the vaccine.
- to present a bill confirming payment of the HPV vaccine.

As for the Slovak Republic, in Italy, CPW funds will be employed for the administration of vaccines to study participants who do not meet the criteria for free administration accordingly to the Italian Legislation. Specifically, the Hospital Pharmacy of ASL Città di Torino will acquire vaccines directly through CPW funds. Participants will therefore be able to get vaccinated for free without paying for the vaccination at the time of administration.

10 COLLECTION OF SPECIMENS, STORAGE, PREPARATION AND TESTING PROCEDURE

WP4 is an interventional study. No collection of specimens is foreseen in the WP4 study protocol.

⁵ Decree of the Ministry of Health No. 585/2008 Coll.

11 ARCHIVES AND COMPUTERIZED DATA

Where: OH medical unit

Who: OH medical staff (medical doctor, research assistant)

What: primary data collected via baseline and follow-up questionnaires, testing results, diagnostic and treatment data

How: archived in local centres according to local protocols and in line with the project's DMP

Each subject will be attributed with a unique, identification number (ID).

The link with the name and other personal information will only be available to authorized staff of the local research team. Forms (hard copies) will be labelled with the corresponding ID and archived in local centres according to the protocols locally available and in line with the CPW project's DMP.

Each raw dataset collected in the implementation centres will be entered in the central data repository via RED Cap, using the eCRF developed by WP1. The management of data will follow the DMP.

12 OVERALL ENROLLMENT FLOWCHART

Effectively, all the stages of subject's recruitment need an effective logging/tracking system in place so that at any time it is easy to see the status of the subjects and where they currently are in the overall process. This will allow monitoring of the process and receiving updates of what is happening. The Figure 1 describes the workflow for case selection.

13 OCCUPATIONAL HEALTHCARE AS A CONTEXT OF IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGIES AND IMPLEMENTATION OUTCOMES

13.1 Background

The CPW project is a study of the implementation of new healthcare practices. Implementation research is the scientific study of methods and strategies that facilitate or hinder the uptake of evidence-based practice and research into regular use. The field of implementation science aims at systematically closing the gap between what we know and what we do by identifying facilitator and addressing barriers related to the implementation of new healthcare practices. It also concerns the impact of implementation strategies (e.g., education of health professionals, reorganisation of working processes) on the uptake of recommended practices (e.g., offer people cancer screening, and follow-up actions if relevant) and contextual factors that influence the uptake (e.g., health professionals competences, characteristics of the organization).

To evaluate the implementation aspects in this project, a process evaluation alongside the implementation will be carried out to capture the complexity inherent in cancer prevention at work. This process evaluation will provide the project with a greater, more in-depth understanding of why the intervention may be more or less effective. This process evaluation will assess the implementation strategies and contextual factors that influence implementation and sustainment (facilitator and barriers). These issues are usually measured with questionnaires for targeted health care professionals (occupational physicians and nurses in CPW). Ideally, the questionnaire is completed by all occupational healthcare providers who are involved in the implementation of preventive testing (physicians, nurses, managers etc.).

13.2 Proposed questionnaire for healthcare providers at the beginning and end of the CPW screening procedures

The questionnaires for occupational healthcare providers (Annexes 8 and 9), and the research team are developed by partner UKHD. The following factors will be assessed using a survey among occupational healthcare providers involved in the delivery of the intervention, patients who receive the intervention, and the local research teams:

Factors	Assessment method		
Practices of screening and follow-up before start of project, incl. collaboration with primary care	Questionnaire for implementation centres	Before start	research teams in centres
Intervention Fidelity (=central implementation outcome)	Questionnaire developed for the specific screening procedure	Follow up	occupational healthcare providers
Context Factors that may have an impact on the implementation	CFIR Questionnaire (quantitative)	Baseline Follow-up	occupational healthcare providers
Barriers and facilitators for implementation	CFIR Questionnaire (quantitative)	Baseline Follow-up	occupational healthcare providers
Intervention Sustainability	Program Sustainability Assessment Tool	Follow-up	occupational healthcare providers
Documentation of planned and realized implementation strategies	Registration forms (e.g., participation in planned trainings, effective referrals for treatment)	Follow up	research teams in centres
Degree of uptake of recommended screening procedures	Questions on reach in the targeted populations	Follow up	research teams in centres

Depending on the local procedure, the questionnaires for healthcare workers and research teams can be subject to inclusion in the ethical application. For centralized data-analysis, data will be shared across centres (including the Heidelberg partner). This will be arranged in the data management plan of the project CPW.

14 ANNEXES

14.1 Annex 1 The Informed consent template

Consent to the processing of personal data

in accordance with Article 6(1)(a) of the Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council (EU) No 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, which repeals Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) (hereinafter referred to as "GDPR") and Act No. 18/2018 Coll. on the protection of personal data and on the amendment of certain acts (hereinafter referred to as "Act No. 18/2018 Coll.").

Data subject:

Name and surname: degree:

birth certificate number: age:e-mail:

phone number: occupation:

I hereby give my voluntary consent to the Regional Authority of Public Health in Banská Bystrica, Cesta k nemocnici 1, 975 56 Banská Bystrica (hereinafter referred to as the "CPW project solver in Slovakia") to collect and process my personal data only for the purpose of creating a cohort (respondent dataset) of the selected population of Slovakia in the interest of strengthening primary prevention against the HPV virus (hereinafter referred to as the "purpose") within the framework of the EU project "Cancer prevention at work" (hereinafter referred to as the „CPW“), on the legal basis of § 6 (a), (b), (c), and (d), § 11 (a), (f), and (t) and § 14 (3) of Act No. 355/2007 Coll. on the protection, support and development of public health and on the amendment and supplementation of certain laws as amended.

In relation to my participation in the CPW project

- Select your answer by circling it.

1. Do I agree to provide personal data in the questionnaires within the project?

I AGREE I DISAGREE

2. Do I agree to receive information about the health risks of human papillomavirus (HPV) infection, including the risk of cancer due to chronic infection?

I AGREE I DISAGREE

3. Do I agree to undergo a diagnostic test for HCV antibodies, which can cause liver inflammation and is a risk factor for liver cancer?

I AGREE I DISAGREE

4. Do I agree to undergo a diagnostic test for Helicobacter pylori antibodies, which can cause inflammatory diseases in the digestive system and may lead to stomach cancer and other digestive system cancers?

I AGREE I DISAGREE

This consent is given for the duration of the purpose of solving the tasks of the CPW project. The data subject has the right to revoke this consent at any time in writing or electronically, in accordance with Section 14 of Act No. 18/2018 Coll. This consent will be kept by the CPW project manager in Slovakia for the period specified in the filing system.

Required information notice:

Personal data processing is governed by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and Act No. 18/2018 Coll.

I am aware of my rights, which are set out in Articles 12 to 23 of the GDPR and in Sections 14, 21 to 24 and 100 of Act No. 18/2018 Coll., which regulate or specify the obligations of the CPW project manager in Slovakia in the implementation of the rights of data subjects.

Statement by the CPW project manager in Slovakia:

CPW Project Manager in Slovakia declares that he/she will not disclose, make available, or provide the personal data of the data subject to third parties, except in cases of release from confidentiality under Section 79(3) of Act No. 18/2018 Coll. Personal data will not be transferred to other countries outside the European Union and also outside the territory of the Slovak Republic. All personal data will be pseudonymized in the form of a code.

The data controller will process personal data only during the duration of the purpose and in the scope necessary to fulfil the purpose (in the scope in which they were provided by the data subject with the addition of the test results). Documents with personal data in electronic form will be deleted from electronic media after the end of the processing purpose and documents in paper form will be destroyed, except for those that must be kept for the following 10 years in accordance with the current legislation of the Slovak Republic.

Data subject declaration:

I, the undersigned, hereby declare and confirm that I have familiarized myself with all the information about the project being solved and contained in this document and my rights under Articles 12 to 23 of the GDPR and Sections 14, 21 to 24 and 100 of Act No. 18/2018 Coll. The information provided is understandable to me and I understand its content. The instruction was provided to me in a clear and comprehensible manner with sufficient explanation of the objectives of the investigations and data collection, and in sufficient time to make a free decision. The information is available to me at the data controller and/or the responsible person.

Date:

handwritten signature of the data subject

Information

of the data subject on the processing of personal data pursuant to Article 13 of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 May 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) (hereinafter referred to as "GDPR") and Act No. 18/2018 Coll. on the Protection of Personal Data and on Amendments to Certain Acts (hereinafter referred to as "Act No. 18/2018 Coll. ").

Operator

Regional Authority of Public Health in Banská Bystrica

Cesta k nemocnici 1, 975 56 Banská Bystrica

Data Protection Officer:

JUDr. PhDr. Marián Nosáľ, PhD.

zodpovedna.osoba.ruvzbb@uvzsr.sk

Processed personal data	name, surname, birth certificate number, age, e-mail, phone number, occupation, subjective opinion on HPV vaccination in a questionnaire, and expression of opinion on the provision of data and biological material (willingness to provide a blood sample for the diagnosis of possible HCV infection – hepatitis C virus, HP – Helicobacter pylori virus). The scope of data is specified in the attached input form for the CPW project respondent.
Purpose of processing	the EU project "Cancer prevention at work" (CPW) aims to design and implement a primary prevention program for cervical cancer and other types of cancer associated with HPV infection through HPV vaccination targeting eligible workers and members of their households in the European population and through innovative citizen-focused strategies to disseminate evidence-based knowledge about the relationship between HPV infection and cancer in humans and the possibility of cancer prevention through HPV vaccination. Our project focuses on HPV vaccination in a selected population
Categories of data subjects	adults (employees) and their family members
Legal basis for processing	the data subject has given consent to the processing of his or her personal data for one or more specific purposes
Retention period	personal data will be kept during the project implementation or until the revocation of the granted consent
Provision of personal data to third parties and disclosure	not being conducted
Cross-border data transfer	being conducted in the form of pseudonymized encoded data
Rights of the data subject under Act No. 18/2018 Coll	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o the right to withdraw consent to the processing of personal data (§ 14); o the right of access to personal data (Art. 21); o the right to rectification of personal data (§ 22); o the right to erasure of personal data (§ 23); o the right to restrict the processing of personal data (§ 24); o the right to lodge a complaint or a motion to initiate proceedings with a supervisory authority, which is the Office for Personal Data Protection (Section 100).

14.2 Annex 2 Baseline questionnaire

BASELINE QUESTIONNAIRE

Baseline (guided) questionnaire - common parts for WP4, WP3

Dear participant,

First of all, we would like to thank you for accepting to participate in this CPW study on prevention issues. Please indicate your responses to the questions on the form. The greatest benefit of the study will be the accuracy of your responses. If you change your answer, then indicate which answer applies. If you do not understand a question, please do not hesitate to ask us. You can also contact us by phone at 0905848300. At any time, you can refuse to answer a specific question or continue to complete the questionnaire.

Your privacy is protected by complying with the requirements of the European General Data Protection Regulation, [Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 May 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, repealing Directive 95/46/EC [and specify relevant national legislation, if applicable]. The [specify name of legal entity] is responsible for the protection of your data against loss, unauthorized access/use, modification/disclosure or other misuse. The Data Controller is [specify (name, function, e.g., study coordinator or director of legal entity)].

All data processing will be done in such a way, that it is no longer possible to attribute your data to you without the use of additional information. Your name will be replaced by a code. Information which identifies you (name, contact details) will be kept separately and under protective measures. All electronic and paper records will be protected from unauthorized access of your private information. Published reports of the study will not contain information that can be traced back to you. Third parties will not have access to your personal results, unless you consent to.

General remark

Within this EC CPW project, the costs of vaccination against HPV will be reimbursed to you after the vaccination, in case you decide to vaccinate yourself and/or your family member(s).

Disclaimer

Some elements in the questionnaire are similar or extracted from the questionnaire used in the project PERCH - Partnership to Contrast HPV co-founded by the European Union.

For local use only – information won't be entered in CPW database

Contact address:

Telephone:

Email:

Full name and surname of the subject:

Interviewer name:

Date of interview: |__| |__| / |__| |__| / |__| |__| |__| |__| (DD/MM/YYYY)

Subject status: |__|

(0=non-eligible (invited and did not come); 1=index participant (worker); 2=participant (family member); 3=refusal)

If "3" please explain reason of refusal:

Identification data

ID number

Country ID __ (SK; IT; RO ...)

Centre acronym __ first 2 capital letters of the acronym (RA for RAPH BB; FD for FDRH; ZP for ZP; UT for UNITO; AS for ASL TO; IS for ISP...)

Number: ____ four digits, starting from the right to the left, i.e., , 0001; 0002; 0003...

Example: SKRA0001 (SK_RA_0001); SKZP0001 (SK_ZP_0001); ITUT0001 (IT_UT_0001).

Part 1: General information

1.1 Sex |__|

(1=male; 2=female; 3=other/undisclosed)

1.2 Nationality (example: SK, IT) (according to ISO 3166-1; ALPHA 2 coding system). |__| |__|

1.3 Date of birth

Day|_|_| Month |_|_| Year |_|_|_|_|_|_|or
(If date of birth not available, or not transferable): **Age** |_|_|

1.4 Highest education completed |_|_|

(1=primary; 2=undergraduate; 3=university (Bc, Mgr. (Master), M.D., Ing.)

1.5 Age at completion of full-time education |_|_|

1.6 Living place |_|_| (1=rural; 2=urban)

1.7 Marital status |_|_|

(1=single; 2=married; 3=living (cohabitating) with a partner but not married; 4=divorced; 5=widowed; 6=prefer not to disclose)

1.8 Number of children in family (list all children in the family) |_|_|

Child 1. Age |_|_|

Child 2. Age |_|_|

Child 3. Age |_|_|

Child 4. Age |_|_|

1.9 Who do you cohabitate with, i.e., , who are you living with in one household? Please indicate the numbers for each category.

|_| Partner/spouse |_| Children |_| Nobody, I live alone

|_| Parents |_| Other relatives

|_| Friends |_| Flatmates/roommates (that do not qualify as friends)

Part 2: Medical history

2.1 Have you ever had any of the following diseases/conditions confirmed by a doctor? |__|

(0=definitely or probably no; 1=definitely or probably yes; 3=I don't know/I'm unsure; 9=refuse to answer)

	Disease If yes, mark all concerned	When it was first diagnosed (year, approximately)?	Treatment Were you prescribed a treatment by a doctor? (0=No; 1=Yes; 3=I don't know/I'm unsure;
2.1.1	__ Diabetes	_ _ _ _ _ _ _	__
2.1.2	__ Hypertension	_ _ _ _ _ _ _	__
2.1.3	__ Hepatitis B	_ _ _ _ _ _ _	__
2.1.4	__ Hepatitis C	_ _ _ _ _ _ _	__
2.1.5	__ Hepatitis D	_ _ _ _ _ _ _	__
2.1.6	__ HIV	_ _ _ _ _ _ _	__
2.1.7	__ Sexually transmitted infections (including HPV)	_ _ _ _ _ _ _	__
2.1.8	__ Renal failure	_ _ _ _ _ _ _	__
2.1.9	__ Haematological disorders	_ _ _ _ _ _ _	__
2.1.10	__ Organ, tissue, cell transplant	_ _ _ _ _ _ _	__
2.1.11	__ Cancer If yes: site of origin/type __ __ (1=mouth or pharynx; 2=oesophagus; 3=stomach; 4=colon or rectum; 5=pancreas; 6=liver; 7=larynx; 8=lung; 9=melanoma; 10=breast; 11=cervix of uterus; 12=other uterus; 13=prostate; 14=bladder; 15=kidney; 16=thyroid gland; 17=leukaemia and lymphoma; 18=other; unknown or more than one site)	_ _ _ _ _ _ _	__
2.1.12	Other severe disease/condition (please fill in):	_ _ _ _ _ _ _	__

2.2 Have you ever had blood transfusion? |__|

(0=no; 1=yes; 3=I don't know/I'm unsure; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes, when it was the last one (year): |_|_|_|_|_|_|_|_|

2.3 Have you ever had treatment with blood derivatives/component (e.g., red blood cell concentrates or suspension, platelets, plasma, cryoprecipitate, albumin, coagulation factors, immunoglobulins)?

|__|

(0=no; 1=yes; 3=I don't know/I'm unsure; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes, when it was the last one (year): |_|_|_|_|_|_|_|_|

2.4 Have you ever had dialysis treatment? |__|

(0=no; 1=yes; 3=I don't know/I'm unsure; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes, when it was the last one (year): |_|_|_|_|_|_|_|_|

2.5 Have you ever had endoscopic procedures? (e.g., colonoscopy, oesophagus-gastro-duodenoscopy, bronchoscopy, arthroscopy, etc.)? |__|

(0=no; 1=yes; 3=I don't know/I'm unsure; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes, when it was the last one (year): |_|_|_|_|_|_|_|_|

2.6 Have you ever been given an injection treatment? |__|

(0=no; 1=yes; 3=I don't know/I'm unsure; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes, when it was the last one (year): |__||__||__||__|

2.7 Have you ever had intramuscular or intravenous administration of any substance with non-sterile syringes/devices? |__|

(0=no; 1=yes; 3=I don't know/I'm unsure; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes, when it was the last one (year): |__||__||__||__|

2.8 Have you ever had acupuncture with non-disposable needles/devices? |__|

(0=no; 1=yes; 3=I don't know/I'm unsure; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes, when it was the last one (year): |__||__||__||__|

2.9 Have you ever had tattoos? |__|

(0=no; 1=yes; 3=I don't know/I'm unsure; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes, when it was the last one (year): |__||__||__||__|

2.10 Have you ever had piercing? |__|

(0=no; 1=yes; 3=I don't know/I'm unsure; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes, when it was the last one (year): |__||__||__||__|

2.11 Are you blood donor? |__|

(0=no; 1=yes; 3=I don't know/I'm unsure; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes, when it was the last one (year): |__||__||__||__|

2.12 Have you ever had dental treatment, intervention or dental surgery? |__|

(0=no; 1=yes; 3=I don't know/I'm unsure; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes, when it was the last one (year): |__||__||__||__|

2.13 Have you ever been vaccinated against Hepatitis B? |__|

(0=no; 1=yes; 3=I don't know/I'm unsure; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes:

2.13.1 When did you received the last dose of vaccine?

year |__||__||__||__|

age |__||__|

Only for women

2.14 Are you pregnant now? |__|

(0=no; 1=yes; 3=I don't know/I'm unsure; 9=refuse to answer)

2.15 Have you ever been pregnant? |__|

(0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes:

2.15.1 How many deliveries have you had? (Please consider children born alive or dead after 5 months pregnancy) |__|__|

Would you like to comment or add more details?

.....

Part 3: Family medical history

3.1 First degree relative has/ had cancer |__|
(1=yes; 2=no)

3.2 If yes, mark all concerned.

|__| Mother |__| Father
|__| Brother/ Sister |__| Grandparents

3.3 If yes, please mention where the cancer was localized (mark all concerned).

|__| Stomach |__| Colorectal
|__| Liver |__| Uterus
|__| Breast |__| Not sure
|__| Other:

3.4 Did any of your close relatives (those listed above plus your parents), living in the same household, ever suffer from Hepatitis B, C, D? |__|
(0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes, please specify who and which type of Hepatitis:

Part 4: Occupational history

4.1 Recent occupation / Job title:

4.2 Your main type of activity at this job (describe):

ISCO - 08 code |__| |__| |__| |__| |__| (Recent occupation to be filled out by research team.)

4.3 Please list below any occupation or jobs you have held for at least 10 years.

If you had more than one occupation for 10 years or more, then start with the first job you had after you left school.

4.3.1 From: year |__| |__| |__| |__| to year |__| |__| |__| |__| and/or
From: age |__| |__| to age |__| |__|

4.3.2 From: year |__| |__| |__| |__| to year |__| |__| |__| |__| and/or
From: age |__| |__| to age |__| |__|

4.3.3 From: year |__| |__| |__| |__| to year |__| |__| |__| |__| and/or
From: age |__| |__| to age |__| |__|

4.4 Have you ever been exposed to any biological hazards (human tissue, organs, blood, biological fluids, etc.) at your work? |__|
(0=no; 1=yes; 3=I don't know/I'm unsure; 9=refuse to answer)

4.5 Do you wear personal protective equipment at work? |__|
(0=no; 1=yes; 3=I don't know/I'm unsure; 9=refuse to answer)

4.6 Have you ever experienced any injury with biological contamination risk (prick, cut, etc.) at your recent work? |__|
(0=no; 1=yes; 3=I don't know/I'm unsure; 9=refuse to answer)

4.7 Have you ever been exposed to any chemical hazards (toxic or noxious substances, carcinogens, mutagens) or to ionising radiation at your work? |__|
(0=no; 1=yes; 3=I don't know/I'm unsure; 9=refuse to answer)

Would you like to comment or add more details?

Part 5: Body size

5.1 How tall are you?

|__| |__| |__| cm

5.2 How much do you weigh?

|__| |__| |__| kg

5.3 How much did you weigh about 2 years ago?

|__| |__| |__| kg

Would you like to comment or add more details?

Part 6: Diet

6.1 Would you describe your diet as healthy? |__|

(0=no, 1=somewhat, 2=yes)

6.2 How often do you usually eat the following food items?

(1=never; 2=less than once a month; 3=1-3 times a month; 4=once or twice a week; 5=most days but not every day; 6=every day; 7=unknown/refuse to answer)

|__| red meat (i.e., beef, veal, pork, lamb, mutton, horse and goat meat)

|__| poultry (i.e., chicken and turkey)

|__| processed* meat, including ham, salami, sausages, etc.

|__| fish

|__| fresh fruits (i.e., apples, pears, orange and other citrus fruits, bananas, berries, etc.)

|__| raw vegetables (i.e., green salads, tomatoes, etc., according the season)

|__| cooked green/leafy vegetables (i.e., spinach, artichokes, asparagus, green beans, etc.)

|__| dairy products (i.e., milk, yoghurts, cheese, butter, etc.)

|__| cookies, biscuits, chocolates, cakes and sweets

|__| soft drinks (e.g., cola)

*Salted, smoked, or processed with any other preservation method.

CPW MODULE WP4 - Prevention of the HPV related cancer

Part 7: Knowledge about HPV infection

This section is devoted to the issue of HPV. Please answer as truthfully as you can. Whether or not you answer the questions will not affect you in any way. If you are not comfortable answering a question, just leave it blank. This is not a test. There are no right and wrong answers. If you do not find an answer that fits exactly, mark the one that comes closest. Please read every question and mark your best answer for each question.

7.1 Do you think HPV can cause different types of cancer? |__|

(0=no, 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)

7.2 Do you think HPV can cause cancer of the cervix uteri? |__|

(0=no, 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)

- 7.3 Do you think HPV can cause cancer of vagina, vulva (female genitals)? |__|
(0=no, 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)
- 7.4 Do you think HPV can cause penile cancer? |__|
(0=no, 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)
- 7.5 Do you think HPV can cause cancer in anal and rectal area? |__|
(0=no, 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)
- 7.6 Do you think HPV can cause cancer in the back of the throat, including the base of the tongue, tonsils, pharynx and larynx? |__|
(0=no, 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)
- 7.7 Do you think that some types of HPV cause genital warts? |__|
(0=no, 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)
- 7.8 Do you think that HPV infection is a sexually transmitted disease? |__|
(0=no, 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)
- 7.9 Do you think HPV can infect a person without visible symptoms? |__|
(0=no, 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)
- 7.10 Do you think HPV infections are rare? |__|
(0=no, 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)
- 7.11 Do you think that some cases of cervical cancer are not caused by HPV infection? |__|
(0=no, 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)
- 7.12 Do you think both men and women can be infected with HPV? |__|
(0=no, 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)
- 7.13 Do you think that only women can be infected with HPV? |__|
(0=no, 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)
- 7.14 Do you think that some HPV infections resolve spontaneously? |__|
(0=no, 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)
- 7.15 Do you think that you, your partner or children may be exposed to the risk of HPV infection now or in the future? |__|
(0=no, 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)
- 7.16 Do you know that in countries with established HPV vaccination programs there was a significant decrease in cervical cancer incidence (dropped by around 90 %)? |__|
(0=no, 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)

Part 8: Female questionnaire

- 8.1 Do you participate in preventive gynaecological check-ups? |__|
(0=no; 1=yes; 2=I don't know; 9=I prefer not to answer)
- If yes:
- 8.1.1 If yes, in what frequency were they? |__|
(1=once per year; 2=at least once; 3=I refuse to answer)
- 8.1.2 In which year was your last check-up?
|__| |__| |__| |__| YYYY
- 8.2 Have you ever been screened /tested for HPV infection or cervical tissue changes? |__|
(0=no; 1=yes; 2=I don't know; 9=I prefer not to answer)

If yes:

8.2.1 What type of test was it? |

(1=PAP (cytology); 2=HPV DNA test; 3=I don't know)

8.2.2 What was the result? |

(0=negative; 1=positive; 3= I don't know; 9=I refuse to answer)

8.2.3 In case of positive result, have you got medical treatment of the uterine cervix? |

(0=no; 1=yes; 2=treatment is ongoing; 3= I don't know; 9=I refuse to answer)

Part 9: Knowledge about vaccination against HPV

9.1 Do you know that there is a vaccination that prevent HPV caused infection and HPV caused cancer? | (0=no; 1=yes; 3=I don't know/ I'm unsure; 9=I refuse to answer)

9.2 Do you know by who you and/or your family member could be vaccinated against HPV? |

(0=no; 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)

9.3 Do you know that fully reimbursed vaccines (vaccination) against HPV are intended for children up to 15 years of age? |

(0=no; 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)

9.4 Do you think HPV vaccines work better if given before age 15? |

(0=no; 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)

9.5 Do you think HPV vaccines can also be administered to adults up to 45 years of age? |

(0=no; 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)

9.6 Do you think HPV vaccines protect against all types of HPV? |

(0=no; 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)

9.7 Have you been vaccinated against HPV infection? |

(0=no; 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)

9.8 Has your doctor offered you the opportunity to be vaccinated against HPV? |

(0=no; 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)

If yes:

9.8.1 Which speciality doctor? |

(1=GP; 2=gynaecologist; 3=urologist; 4=dermatologist; 5=other)

9.9 Do you want to be vaccinated against HPV within the framework of this project? |

(0=no; 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)

9.10 Has your partner or children already been vaccinated against HPV? |

(0=no; 1=I don't think so; 2=I'm unsure; 3=I think so; 4=yes)

If yes:

9.10.1 Who has been vaccinated?

| Partner

| Child 1

| Child 2

| Child 3

| Child 4

9.11 Do you want to take the opportunity to vaccinate your family member (partner, children) against HPV within the framework of this project? |

(0=no; 1=yes; 3=I don't know/ I'm unsure; 9=I refuse to answer)

If yes:

9.11.1 Who will get the vaccination?

<input type="checkbox"/> Partner	Age	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>	Sex	<input type="text"/>	m/f/other/undisclosed
<input type="checkbox"/> Child 1	Age	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>	Sex	<input type="text"/>	m/f/other/undisclosed
<input type="checkbox"/> Child 2	Age	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>	Sex	<input type="text"/>	m/f/other/undisclosed
<input type="checkbox"/> Child 3	Age	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>	Sex	<input type="text"/>	m/f/other/undisclosed
<input type="checkbox"/> Child 4	Age	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>	Sex	<input type="text"/>	m/f/other/undisclosed

If you are **against HPV vaccination**, please answer the questions in **Part 10** (not part 11).

If you are **interested in HPV vaccination**, please answer the questions in **Part 11** (not part 10).

Part 10: Reasons for refusal of HPV vaccination (multiple answers possible)

10.1 What are your reasons for refusing the HPV vaccination? (possibility of multiple answers)

- Fear of an unwanted event.
- No confidence in the HPV vaccine.
- Insufficient information about HPV vaccination.
- No confidence in vaccination in general.
- Only for daughters: It is not necessary to vaccinate, as a regular pap test/HPV-DNA test can prevent cervical cancer.
- It is not necessary to get vaccinated because our child is young and not sexually active.
- Vaccination against HPV is not helpful.
- Vaccination against HPV is not mandatory.
- GP / Paediatrician recommendation against HPV vaccination.
- Another medical doctor recommendation against HPV vaccination.
- Another health care worker recommendation against HPV vaccination.
- Advice from acquaintances/friends against HPV vaccination.
- Anti- vaccine promotion campaign.
- Vaccination against HPV promotes risk sexual behaviour.
- Fear of injection.
- HPV infection is not serious.
- The child has contraindications against HPV vaccine, which was confirmed by his/her doctor.
- An alternative medical approach that does not include vaccinations.
- We missed the deadline for vaccination.
- We didn't know that the HPV vaccine is free for 12-year-olds.
- Religious concerns.
- Other - please specify:

If you are interested in HPV vaccination, please answer the questions in part 11.

Part 11: HPV vaccine administration

11.1 Where do you want to get vaccinated against HPV?

(1=GP practice; 2=OHS service; 3=gynaecologist; 4=urologist; 5=dermatologist; 6=another specialist)

Write the surname of the doctor or the name of the outpatient clinic where you wish to have the HPV vaccination:

11.2 Where do you plan to vaccinate your family member(s) against HPV? (Connected to answer to question 9.11.1)

List by family member decided for HPV vaccination and where he/she/they want to get vaccinated. Write the name and surname of the doctor or the name of the outpatient clinic where you wish to get vaccinated

against HPV the family member(s) and his/her speciality (GP, paediatrician, gynaecologist, urologist, another specialist).

Who will get the vaccination?		Vaccinating doctor	
		Name and surname	Speciality of MD
11.2.1	Partner		
11.2.2	Child 1		
11.2.3	Child 2		
11.2.4	Child 3		
11.2.5	Child 4		
11.2.6		

14.3 Annex 3 Self-administrated baseline questionnaire

SELF-ADMINISTRATED BASELINE QUESTIONNAIRE

Self-administrated questionnaire - HCV and HPV intervention

(pseudonymous questionnaire)

ID Number: _____

Before you start, please read this:

This questionnaire is part of the study on HPV and hepatitis C prevention (*to be corrected in study centre as appropriate*) that you agreed to enter to participate. The information you give will contribute to a better understanding of personal lifestyle and opinions.

DO NOT WRITE YOUR NAME on this questionnaire. The answers you give will be kept completely private. No one will know what you write. The information will not be used to find out your name. No names will ever be reported.

Answer the questions based on what you really do and know. Please answer as truthfully as you can. Whether or not you answer the questions will not affect you in any way. If you are not comfortable answering a question, just leave it blank.

This is not a test. There are no right and wrong answers. If you do not find an answer that fits exactly, mark the one that comes closest. Please read every question and mark your best answer for each question.

We hope you find the questionnaire interesting. If you have a question, please ask and our staff will assist you.

When you have finished, please put the questionnaire into [the enclosed box next to the desk] [the sealed envelope] etc.

Please begin

1. HEALTH STATUS AND SOCIAL ISSUES

1.1 Which statement would best describe your health status?

- I generally feel absolutely healthy.
- I only experience minor health issues from time to time.
- I have major and/or chronic health issues.
- I am constantly sick.

1.2 Which statement would best describe your understanding of health, health practices, and health issues?

- I am fully aware of my health issues and also have a solid understanding of other health matters.
- I am fully aware of my health issues, their causes, and how I should take care of myself.
- I understand I have some health issues, but I don't know exactly why and what to do about it.
- My doctor tells me that I have severe health issues, but I do not really understand what it means and what I should do with this.

1.3 When you have health issues, who do you discuss (trust) these with? Multiple answers allowed.

- occupational specialist at work family doctor or other healthcare professional
- partner/spouse children
- parents other relatives
- friends

1.4 Please mark your answer on the scale which applies to you.

1.4.1 Things that happen in my life most often depend on

Circumstances, situations and other people	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	My own decisions, efforts and behaviour
--	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----	---

1.4.2 To what extent do you feel responsible for your health?

To very little extent	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	To a great extent
-----------------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----	-------------------

1.5 Household income (self-evaluation) (1=low; 2=low-to-middle; 3=middle; 4=middle-to-high; 5=high)

Would you like to comment or add more details?

1.6 Do you have savings/financial funds that (in case of losing your income) could cover your expenses for at least 3 subsequent months? (0=no; 1=yes)

1.7 Do you have a group of close friends you feel you belong to? (0=no; 1=yes)

If yes:

1.7.1 How often do you meet your close friends?
(0=never; 1=less than once a month; 2=once a month; 3=few times per month; 4=few times per week; 5=everyday/daily)

1.8 Are you skilled at foreign languages? (0=no; 1=yes)

If yes, list all the languages and indicate your proficiency level. (1=basic; 2=good; 3=mother tongue)

- 1.8.1 Reading Speaking Writing
- 1.8.2 Reading Speaking Writing
- 1.8.3 Reading Speaking Writing

2. TOBACCO USE

2.1 Did you smoke cigarettes in the past year? |__|
(0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes:

2.1.1 How many cigarettes per day on average ("cigarettes" including hand rolled ignore vaping, pipe and cigar smoking)? |__| |__|

2.1.2 At what age did you start smoking? (i.e., using cigarettes on most days) |__| |__|

2.1.3 How many years have you smoked? |__| |__|

If no:

2.1.4 Have you ever smoked cigarettes on most days for at least one year? |__|
(0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer)

2.1.5 How many cigarettes did you smoke per day on average? ("cigarettes" including hand rolled, ignore vaping, pipe and cigar smoking) |__| |__|

2.1.6 At what age did you start smoking on most days? |__| |__|

2.1.7 At what age did you stop smoking? |__| |__|

3. ALCOHOL USE

3.1. Do you drink any alcohol? |__|
(0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes:

3.1.1 How often do you have a drink containing alcohol? |__|
(0=less than monthly; 1=monthly; 2=weekly; 3=daily or almost daily)

3.1.2 How many days per week would you have some alcohol? |__| (0-7; 0 means none in most weeks)

3.1.3 How much of the following alcoholic beverages do you usually drink per week?

3.1.3.1 Distillate/vodka or other strong drinks (40% ethanol)

Quantity/week: |__| |__| |__| |__| Unit: |__| glasses (0,5dcl) |__| bottles (1l)

3.1.3.2 Wine

Quantity/week: |__| |__| |__| |__| Unit: |__| glasses (2dcl) |__| bottles (1l)

3.1.3.3 Beer

Quantity/week: |__| |__| |__| |__| Unit: |__| glasses (0,5l) |__| bottles (0,5l)

Are there any other comments you would like to make with regard to alcohol use?

(Please, type)

4. OTHER SUBSTANCE USE

4.1. How many times IN YOUR LIFE (if any) have you used any of the following drugs?

Mark one box in each row.

Substances/ Drugs	Never	Tried once or twice	Irregular use	Regular use (weekly, monthly, yearly)
4.1.1 Marijuana (grass, pot) or hashish (hash, hash oil)				
4.1.2 Tranquillizers or sedatives (without a doctor or medical worker telling you to do so)				
4.1.3 Amphetamines (uppers, pep pills, bennies, speed)				
4.1.4 Methamphetamine				
4.1.5 Ecstasy				
4.1.6 LSD				
4.1.7 Other hallucinogens (for example "magic mushrooms")				
4.1.8 Relevin				
4.1.9 Cocaine				
4.1.10 Crack				
4.1.11 Pervitin				
4.1.12 Heroin (smack, horse)				
4.1.13 Other opiates (without a doctor or medical worker telling you to do so)				
4.1.14 Drugs by injection with a needle (heroin, cocaine, amphetamine)				
4.1.15 Solvents or inhalants (glue, toluen, etc.)				

Are there any other comments you would like to make with regard to other substances use?

.....

5. OTHER HEALTH RELATED ISSUES

5.1 Within the last year, have you been tested for sexually transmitted diseases (STD)? |__|
(0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes:

5.1.1 Which STD test did you get? Please mark.

- |__| HIV
- |__| Syphilis
- |__| Gonorrhoea
- |__| Trichomoniasis
- |__| other, please specify:

5.2 The results of the test were |__| (0=negative; 1=positive; 9=refuse to answer)

5.3 Do you identify as: |__| (1=gay; 2=lesbian; 3=straight; 4=bisexual; 5=other)

5.4 Have you ever been/are you sexually active with another person? |__| (0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes:

5.4.1 What is/are the gender(s) of your sex partner(s)? |__| M; |__| F; |__| other;

5.4.2 How many sexual partners have you had in the last year? |__| |__|

5.4.3 Do you and your partner(s) use STI prevention tools (male/female condoms, other tools)?
|__| (0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer)

5.5 Have you ever been tested for Hepatitis? (0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes:

5.5.1 When was the test ||||/||||||||| (DD/MM/YYYY)

5.5.2 The results of the test were: (1=positive; 2=negative; 9=refuse to answer)

5.5.3 What type of test it was? (1= for hepatitis B; 2= for hepatitis C; 9=refuse to answer)

5.5.4 Where did you get tested: (1=GP physician; 2=occupational health physician; 3=blood donation; 4=other)

If other- please specify:

6. OPINION ON HCV TESTING AND CANCER PREVENTION AT WORKPLACE

6.1 Before entering this study was you aware of the risk factors for liver cancer?

(0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer)

6.2 Before entering this study was you aware of the risks of HCV infection?

(0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes:

6.2.1 From where did you get the information: (1=GP physician; 2=occupational health physician; 3=other physician; 4=colleagues/ friends; 5=social media; 6=mass media (TV, radio, papers); 7=nobody; 8=other)

If other- please specify:

6.3 Are you positive about carrying out the HCV testing in the workplace?

(0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer)

6.4 Do you think this will make it easier to implement for you?

(0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer)

6.5 Do you think you were given adequate information before taking the screening test?

(0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer)

6.6 If you test positive for HCV, would you be inclined to undergo antiviral therapy?

(0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer)

Are there any other comments you would like to make?

7. GENERAL QUESTIONS ON HUMAN PAPILLOMA VIRUS (HPV)

7.1 Did you have any information about the risks of HPV infection before entering this study?

(0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer)

7.2 What/who were the sources of this information (multiple answers possible)?

(1=GP physician/pediatrician; 2=occupational health physician; 3=other physician (gynaecologist, urologist, dermatologist, etc.); 4=colleagues/ friends/ family members; 5=school; 6=mass media (TV, radio, papers, internet, social networking sites, etc.); 7=nobody; 8=other)

If other- please specify:

7.3 Have you ever participated in any study focused on HPV infection detection, intervention or treatment? (0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes:

7.3.1 Write the name of the study (or description of the study type) and period of participation.

.....

|||| YYYY

8. OTHER ASPECTS

8.1 Have you ever living in any type of enclosure setting, deprived of liberty (i.e., war/labor camps, social, mental care facilities etc.)? (0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes:

8.1.1 When it was (year): |__| |__| |__| |__|

8.1.2 For how long you have been in the enclosure setting?

8.2 Have you ever been in prison? (0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes:

8.2.1 When it was (year): |__| |__| |__| |__|

8.2.2 For how long you have been in prison?

8.3 Is religious/spiritual practice important to you?

(0=never; 1=yes, still; 2=yes, only in the past; 9=refuse to answer)

If yes (current and past):

8.3.1 How often is/was it?

Number of times per week |__| |__| |__| |__|

How long is/was it? (min each time) |__| |__| |__| |__|

8.3.2 At what level do you usually practice?

(1=individual; 1=family; 3=social network; 3=organized events)

Are there any other comments you would like to make?

Note to the study centre:

The next part of the questionnaire needs to be pre-labelled with the participant code;

The next part of the questionnaire needs to be mailed at the following address

[Department of Business and Management](#)
[Att. Anna Schneider-Kamp & Tija Rageliene](#)
[Campusvej 55 / 5230 Odense M / Denmark](#)

ID number – The same as for the self-admin questionnaire

Note to the participant:

Consider the big circle below as a representation of your general health. Examine the list provided and indicate the importance you attribute to each item for your health within the big circle. Use circles of varying sizes to signify their importance. Label each circle with the corresponding number from the list. For example, if a participant considers their age highly relevant to their health, their job role somewhat relevant, and their neighbours nearly irrelevant, that participant might draw something like this:

My Health

Example list and drawing.

1. My age
2. My job role
3. My neighbors

Now, please proceed as follows: First, examine the list numbered 1 to 12 below. Then, draw the circles to illustrate the importance of each item to your health. Finally, label each circle with the corresponding number from the list.

How important are each of these for your health?

1. Relationships with my family members
2. Relationships with my friends
3. Diseases in my family's history
4. Communication with health care specialists (for ex. GP, nurses, doctors, etc.)
5. Foreign languages I can understand.
6. Availability of information about health and diseases
7. Government attention/support to the health care system
8. My income
9. High quality food (for ex. organic, ecological)
10. Availability of new digital technologies OR technologies that I use (mobile, PC, web, smartwatch...).
11. My education
12. How well I can handle stress.

My Health

THANK YOU FOR YOUR COLLABORATION!

THE INTERVIEW IS FINISHED.
THANK YOU FOR YOUR COLLABORATION!

14.4 Annex 4 Protocol to assess worker's self-perceived health capital

University of Southern Denmark / Department of Business and Social Science

Projective Technique to Assess Worker's Self-Perceived Health Capital

CPW WP5 Research Protocol

Projective techniques are an approach to gaining insights into people's understandings and imageries in contexts where the response to a direct questionnaire may be complex to obtain or where socially acceptable, but not necessarily truthful responses might be expected. There is a wide range of projective techniques with a common origin in clinical psychiatry that have been adapted and are currently being used in social sciences. Projective techniques are employed in varying degrees in consumer, education and health research since they allow participants to express those thoughts and feelings that can be difficult to access by direct questioning. This is achieved by presenting participants with ambiguous verbal or visual stimulus materials. Importantly, projective techniques can also be fun and therefore engaging for participants to perform (Belk, Ger & Askegaard 1997; Catterall & Ibbotson, 2000; Gambaro, 2018; Wiehagen et al., 2007).

Therefore, projective techniques might be a suitable methodology to be employed for research on health-related topics in different cultural settings, particularly in those settings where qualitative data collection might prove difficult because of the language barrier. *The aim of using the expression as projective circle technique is to explore workers' perceptions of the social, cultural, economic resources, and personal antecedents constituting their health capital* (Schneider-Kamp, 2021; Schneider-Kamp et al. 2021; Schneider-Kamp and Askegaard, 2022; Schneider-Kamp et al. 2023). See figure 1 for an illustration of the patient-centric parts of the health capital model.

Fig. 1. The health capital model underlying the proposed projective circle technique.

Procedure: After filling the baseline questionnaire, participants will be asked to perform a projective technique task. Using the proposed projective circle technique, the participants will be asked to think about different health-related aspects that serve as proxies for the resources that comprise health capital. The participants are tasked to draw these aspects as the smaller circles inside the bigger circle which represents their overall health. The collected data will be sent by post to SDU researchers, where it will be coded in terms of the relative size of different circles drawn by the participants. This means that each circle size is coded by comparing it with other circle sizes inside the big circle which represents the overall health of a participant. The sizes are coded into up to 5 categories: *very large*, *large*, *medium*, *small*, and *very small*. Then this data will be analyzed together with the data collected through the baseline questionnaire.

Tools: Paper and pencil

Method: self-administered

Participants: N=300

Duration: 5-10 min

Instructions to the participant (worded as clearly and simple as possible):

“Consider the big circle below as a representation of your general health. Examine the list provided and indicate the importance you attribute to each item for your health within the big circle. Use circles of varying sizes to signify their importance. Label each circle with the corresponding number from the list. For example, if a participant considers their age highly relevant to their health, their job role somewhat relevant, and their neighbors nearly irrelevant, that participant might draw something like this:

Example list and drawing.

4. My age
5. My job role
6. My neighbors

Now, please proceed as follows: First, examine the list numbered 1 to 12 below. Then, draw the circles to illustrate the importance of each item to your health. Finally, label each circle with the corresponding number from the list.

How important are each of these for your health?

1. Relationships with my friends
2. Relationships with my family members
3. Diseases in my family's history
4. Communication with health care specialists (for ex. GP, nurses, doctors, etc.)
5. Government attention/support to the health care system
6. Availability of information about health and diseases
7. My educational background
8. Foreign languages I can understand.
9. Access to digital technologies (e.g., smartphone, computer fitness tracker)
10. Money for buying medicine and paying for health services
11. Money for purchasing healthy high-quality foods (e.g., organic, ecological)
12. How well I can handle stress.

Example of the task performed.

Baseline Questionnaire |__|

(0=no/missing; 1=Yes; 2=pending; 9= refuse to answer the questionnaire)

Follow-up Questionnaire |__|

(0=no/missing; 1=Yes; 2=pending; 9= refuse to answer the questionnaire)

Have you already had a confirmed HPV infection? |__|

(0=no; 1=yes; 2= I have no knowledge)

Has HPV infection occurred in your family? |__|

(0=no; 1=yes; 2= I have no knowledge)

Have you been vaccinated against HPV? |__|

(0=no; 1=yes)

If no - Would you like to get vaccinated against HPV? |__|

(0=no; 1=yes; 2=I'm hesitant)

Would you recommend HPV vaccination to your family members? |__|

(0=no; 1=yes; 2=I'm hesitant)

14.6 Annex 6 Follow-up questionnaire

FOLLOW-UP QUESTIONNAIRE

Subject ID |__||__|/|__||__||__||__|/|__||__||__||__|/|__|

Country ID __ (SK; IT; RO ...)

Centre acronym __ first 2 capital letters of the acronym (RA for RAPH BB; FD for FDRH; ZP for ZP; UT for UNITO; AS for ASL TO; IS for ISP...)

WP number

Current number of the index subject_

Family member of the index subject__

Example:

SK_RA_ WP4_0001= index subject from Regional Authority of Public Health in Banská Bystrica, Slovakia, recruited for HPV

SK_RA_ WP4_0001_01= family member of the SK_RA_ WP4_0001, recruited for HPV

Date of follow up interview: |__|__ |/|__|__ |/|__|__ ||__|__ | (DD/MM/YYYY)

Contacted via |__|

1=direct interview

2=telephone

3=(e)mail

4=other

Subject status: |__|

1=participant (worker)

2=participant (family member)

3=refusal

If "3" please explain reason of refusal.....

1. Have you follow the medical recommendation to be vaccinated against HPV? |__|

(0=NO / 1= YES)

If YES – continue here

1.1 When were you vaccinated against HPV?

.....

1.2 Where were you vaccinated against HPV?

.....

1.3 Who vaccinated you? (Enter the name of the clinic and the name of the vaccinating doctor)

.....

1.4 Could you provide a doctor's confirmation/exchange letter/of the vaccination against HPV?

|__| (0=NO / 1= YES)

1.5 Could you provide a bill for the vaccine from the pharmacy in order to get a reimbursement from the CPW project funds? |__| (0=NO / 1= YES)

1.6 Please indicate the bank account number to reimburse you for the HPV vaccine:

.....

1.7 Have you experienced any adverse side effects after vaccination? If yes, please specify:

.....

1.8 When did you receive the second dose of the HPV vaccine?

.....

1.9 Where were you vaccinated against HPV?

.....

1.10 Who vaccinated you? (Enter the name of the clinic and the name of the vaccinating doctor)

.....

1.11 Can you please provide a doctor's confirmation /exchange letter/ of the vaccination against HPV? |__| (0=NO / 1= YES)

1.12 Could you provide a bill for the vaccine from the pharmacy in order to get a reimbursement from the CPW project funds? |__| (0=NO / 1= YES)

1.13 Please indicate the bank account number to reimburse you for the HPV vaccine:

.....

1.14 Have you experienced any adverse side effects after vaccination? If yes, please specify:

.....

1.15 When did you receive the third dose of the HPV vaccine?

.....

1.16 Where were you vaccinated against HPV?

.....

1.17 Who vaccinated you? (Enter the name of the clinic and the name of the vaccinating doctor)
.....

1.18 Can you please provide a doctor's confirmation/ exchange letter of the vaccination against HPV? |__| (0=NO / 1= YES)

1.19 Can you please provide a bill for the vaccine from the pharmacy in order to get a reimbursement from the CPW project funds? |__| (0=NO / 1= YES)

1.20 Please indicate the bank account number to reimburse you for the HPV vaccine:
.....

1.21 Have you experienced any adverse side effects after vaccination? If yes, please specify:
.....

If NO- continue here

- |__| The health care setting recommended was far from (my) residence.
- |__| The health care services recommended where not appropriate (for me) they.
- |__| I do not have medical insurance coverage.
- |__| I postponed the decision due to personal problems.
- |__| other (please write)

2. Have you follow the medical recommendation to vaccinate your family member..... (to be completed) to be vaccinated against HPV infection?

If YES for vaccination, continue here

2.1 When was your **family member** (indicate first and last name, date of birth) vaccinated against HPV in the framework of the project CPW?
.....

2.2 Where and by whom was your family member vaccinated?
.....

2.3 Can you please provide a doctor's confirmation/exchange letter/ of the vaccination against HPV? |__| (0=NO / 1= YES)

2.4 Can you please provide a bill for the vaccine from the pharmacy in order to get a reimbursement from the CPW project funds? |__| (0=NO / 1= YES)

2.5 Please indicate the bank account number in order to reimburse you the cost:
.....

2.6 Have they experienced any adverse side effects after vaccination? If yes, please specify:
.....

2.7 When did they receive the second dose of the HPV vaccine?
.....

- 2.8** Where were they vaccinated against HPV?
.....
- 2.9** Who vaccinated them? (Enter the name of the clinic and the name of the vaccinating doctor)
.....
- 2.10** Can you please provide a doctor's confirmation/ exchange letter/ of the vaccination against HPV? (0=NO / 1= YES)
- 2.11** Can you please provide a bill for the vaccine from the pharmacy to be reimbursed from the CPW project funds? (0=NO / 1= YES)
- 2.12** Please indicate the bank account number in order to reimburse you the cost:
.....
- 2.13** Have they experienced any adverse side effects after vaccination? If yes, please specify:
.....
- 2.14** When did they receive the third dose of the HPV vaccine?
.....
- 2.15** Where were they vaccinated against HPV?
.....
- 2.16** Who vaccinated them? (Enter the name of the clinic and the name of the vaccinating doctor)
.....
- 2.17** Can you please provide a doctor's confirmation/ exchange letter/ of the vaccination against HPV? (0=NO / 1= YES)
- 2.18** Can you please provide a bill for the vaccine from the pharmacy to be reimbursed from the CPW project funds? (0=NO / 1= YES)
- 2.19** Please indicate the bank account number in order to reimburse you the cost:
.....
- 2.20** Have they experienced any adverse side effects after vaccination? If yes, please specify:
.....

If NO- continue here

- The health care setting recommended was far from (my) residence.
- The health care services recommended where not appropriate (for me) they.
- I do not have medical insurance coverage.
- I postponed the decision due to personal problems.
- other (please write)

14.7 Annex 7 Questionnaire for occupational health providers - baseline

Measure: Occupational Healthcare Providers

In the CPW project, new screening practices are implemented in occupational health settings. These are not obligatory by law or regulations, but they could have benefit for individual and population health. This questionnaire aims to document problems and chances for a successful implementation from the perspective of occupational physicians and nurses involved in the delivery of the intervention. Please respond to as many questions as possible. If you truly feel you are not able to answer a question, you may select “Do not know.”

The following questions are about you, your current employment, or your role in the CPW project. Please answer as many questions as possible.

A. Characteristics of participants	
Current Date	__ . __ . 20__
Country	<input type="checkbox"/> Italy <input type="checkbox"/> Spain <input type="checkbox"/> Romania <input type="checkbox"/> Slovakia
Health Institute Company	
CPW – Screening Program (Multiple answers possible)	<input type="checkbox"/> Helicobacteria Pylori <input type="checkbox"/> Hepatitis C <input type="checkbox"/> Human Papilloma Virus
Age	<input type="checkbox"/> below 30 years <input type="checkbox"/> 30 – 39 years <input type="checkbox"/> 40 – 59 years <input type="checkbox"/> 60 years or older
Sex	<input type="checkbox"/> Female <input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Non-Binary <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Prefer not to say
Profession	<input type="checkbox"/> Physician <input type="checkbox"/> Nurse <input type="checkbox"/> Residents Physician <input type="checkbox"/> Other:
Years in practice	<input type="checkbox"/> below 10 years <input type="checkbox"/> 10 – 19 years <input type="checkbox"/> 20 years or longer
Years in current occupational health team	<input type="checkbox"/> below 1 year <input type="checkbox"/> 1 – 4 years <input type="checkbox"/> 5 years or longer

The following questions are related to the screening program that has been implemented at your health institute. Please answer as many questions as possible.

B. About the new screening procedures in CPW						
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know
The proposed new screening procedures come from a reliable source.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
There are many advantages of the new screening procedures with regard to health improvements.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The research evidence for the new screening procedures is sufficiently strong.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I see potential harms of the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The provision of the new screening procedures is sufficiently flexible in practice.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The provision of the new screening procedures is complex in practice.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

The following questions are related to the organisational context at your health institute. Please answer as many questions as possible.

C. About the Organisational Context						
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know
I have sufficient time in my daily practice to implement the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
My place to work is ready for implementing the new screening procedures (e.g., sufficient facilities for testing).	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Information on the new screening procedures for workers is well-organized.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The head of the occupational healthcare team supports the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The employer(s) support the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Follow-up after screening of workers (if required) is well-organized.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The new screening procedures have sufficient priority in my place to work.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
In previous years, my place to work has generally implemented new procedures fast.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Local opinion leaders support the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The organization provides additional support for implementation of the new screening procedures (e.g. resident physicians).	<input type="checkbox"/>					

The following questions are related to your professional role at your health institute. Please answer as many questions as possible.

D. About my role						
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know
My professional attitudes match with the basic principles of the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
From the beginning of the project, I feel involved in the implementation of the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I feel sufficiently competent to implement the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I can exclude individual workers from the new screening procedures for medical reasons.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I perceive resistance from the workers against the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Colleagues in my team convinced me to implement the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I am able to change my operational procedures in daily work to implement the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I feel overstrained with the changes in relation to the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The new screening procedures change my area of work/tasks substantially.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Please complete the following questions if residents' physicians (in training for occupational medicine) are included in the CPW project. Please answer as many questions as possible.

E. About resident physicians						
<i>The involvement of resident physicians ...</i>	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know
... increases the capacity to delivery of new occupational health services, such as the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... requires additional coordination and supervision of activities	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... stimulates critical reflection in our team on the new screening practices	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... supports the conduct of scientific research of the new screening practices	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... is essential for a successful implementation of the new screening practices	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... helps to spread the new screening practices among occupational healthcare providers in my country	<input type="checkbox"/>					

This completes the questionnaire.
Thank you.

14.8 Annex 8 Questionnaire for occupational health providers – follow-up

Measure: Occupational Healthcare Providers

In the CPW project, new screening practices are implemented in occupational health settings. These are not obligatory by law or regulations, but they could have benefit for individual and population health.

This questionnaire aims to document problems and chances for a successful implementation from the perspective of occupational physicians and nurses involved in the delivery of the intervention.

Please respond to as many questions as possible. If you truly feel you are not able to answer a question, you may select “Do not know.”

The following questions are about you, your current employment, or your role in the CPW project. Please answer as many questions as possible.

F. Characteristics of participants	
Current Date	__ . __ . 20__
Country	<input type="checkbox"/> Italy <input type="checkbox"/> Spain <input type="checkbox"/> Romania <input type="checkbox"/> Slovakia
Health Institute Company	
CPW – Screening Program (Multiple answers possible)	<input type="checkbox"/> Helicobacteria Pylori <input type="checkbox"/> Hepatitis C <input type="checkbox"/> Human Papilloma Virus
Age	<input type="checkbox"/> below 30 years <input type="checkbox"/> 30 – 39 years <input type="checkbox"/> 40 – 59 years <input type="checkbox"/> 60 years or older
Sex	<input type="checkbox"/> Female <input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Non-Binary <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Prefer not to say
Profession	<input type="checkbox"/> Physician <input type="checkbox"/> Nurse <input type="checkbox"/> Residents Physician <input type="checkbox"/> Other:
Years in practice	<input type="checkbox"/> below 10 years <input type="checkbox"/> 10 – 19 years <input type="checkbox"/> 20 years or longer
Years in current occupational health team	<input type="checkbox"/> below 1 year <input type="checkbox"/> 1 – 4 years <input type="checkbox"/> 5 years or longer

The following questions are related to the screening program that has been implemented at your health institute. Please answer as many questions as possible.

G. About the new screening procedures in CPW						
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know
The proposed new screening procedures come from a reliable source.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
There are many advantages of the new screening procedures with regard to health improvements.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The research evidence for the new screening procedures is sufficiently strong.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I see potential harms of the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The provision of the new screening procedures is sufficiently flexible in practice.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The provision of the new screening procedures is complex in practice.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

The following questions are related to the organisational context at your health institute. Please answer as many questions as possible.

H. About the Organisational Context						
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know
I have sufficient time in my daily practice to implement the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
My place to work is ready for implementing the new screening procedures (e.g., sufficient facilities for testing).	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Information on the new screening procedures for workers is well-organized.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The head of the occupational healthcare team supports the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The employer(s) support the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Follow-up after screening of workers (if required) is well-organized.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The new screening procedures have sufficient priority in my place to work.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
In previous years, my place to work has generally implemented new procedures fast.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Local opinion leaders support the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The organization provides additional support for implementation of the new screening procedures (e.g., resident physicians).	<input type="checkbox"/>					

The following questions are related to your professional role at your health institute. Please answer as many questions as possible.

I. About my role						
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know
My professional attitudes match with the basic principles of the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
From the beginning of the project, I feel involved in the implementation of the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I feel sufficiently competent to implement the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I can exclude individual workers from the new screening procedures for medical reasons.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I perceive resistance from the workers against the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Colleagues in my team convinced me to implement the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I am able to change my operational procedures in daily work to implement the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I feel overstrained with the changes in relation to the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The new screening procedures change my area of work/tasks substantially.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Please complete the following questions if residents' physicians (in training for occupational medicine) are included in the CPW project. Please answer as many questions as possible.

L. About resident physicians						
<i>The involvement of resident physicians ...</i>	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know
... increases the capacity to delivery of new occupational health services, such as the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... requires additional coordination and supervision of activities	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... stimulates critical reflection in our team on the new screening practices	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... supports the conduct of scientific research of the new screening practices	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... is essential for a successful implementation of the new screening practices	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... helps to spread the new screening practices among occupational healthcare providers in my country	<input type="checkbox"/>					

G. Program Sustainability Assessment Tool

This tool will enable you to assess your program’s current capacity for sustainability across a range of specific organizational and contextual factors. Your responses will identify sustainability strengths and challenges. You can then use results to guide sustainability action planning for your program.

This tool has been designed for use with a wide variety of programs, both large and small, across different settings. Given this flexibility, it is important for you to think through how you are defining your program, organization, and community before starting the assessment.

Below are a few definitions of terms that are frequently used throughout the tool.

- Program refers to the set of formal organized activities that you want to sustain over time. Such activities could occur at the local, state, national, or international level and in a variety of settings.
- Organization encompasses all the parent organizations or agencies in which the program is housed. Depending on your program, the organization may refer to a national, state, or local department, a non-profit organization, a hospital, etc.
- Community refers to the stakeholders who may benefit from or who may guide the program. This could include local residents, organizational leaders, decision-makers, etc. Community does not refer to a specific town or neighbourhood.

In the following questions, you will rate your program across a range of specific factors that affect sustainability. Please respond to as many items as possible. If you truly feel you are not able to answer an item, you may select “NA.”

For each statement, circle the number that best indicates the extent to which your program has or does the following things.

Environmental Support: Having a supportive internal and external climate for your program									
	To little or no extent						To a very great extent		Not able to answer
1. Champions exist who strongly support the program.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	
2. The program has strong champions with the ability to garner resources.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	
3. The program has leadership support from within the larger organization.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	
4. The program has leadership support from outside of the organization.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	
5. The program has strong public support.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	

Funding Stability: Establishing a consistent financial base for your program									
	To little or no extent						To a very great extent		Not able to answer
1. The program exists in a supportive state economic climate.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	
2. The program implements policies to help ensure sustained funding.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	
3. The program is funded through a variety of sources.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	
4. The program has a combination of stable and flexible funding.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	
5. The program has sustained funding.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	

Partnerships: Cultivating connections between your program and its stakeholders

	To little or no extent					To a very great extent		Not able to answer
1. Diverse community organizations are invested in the success of the program.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
2. The program communicates with community leaders.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
3. Community leaders are involved with the program.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
4. Community members are passionately committed to the program.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
5. The community is engaged in the development of program goals.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA

Organizational Capacity: Having the internal support and resources needed to effectively manage your program and its activities								
	To little or no extent					To a very great extent		Not able to answer
1. The program is well integrated into the operations of the organization.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
2. Organizational systems are in place to support the various program needs.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
3. Leadership effectively articulates the vision of the program to external partners.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
4. Leadership efficiently manages staff and other resources.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
5. The program has adequate staff to complete the program's goals.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA

Program Evaluation: Assessing your program to inform planning and document results								
	To little or no extent					To a very great extent		Not able to answer
1. The program has the capacity for quality program evaluation.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
2. The program reports short term and intermediate outcomes.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
3. Evaluation results inform program planning and implementation.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
4. Program evaluation results are used to demonstrate successes to funders and other key stakeholders.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
5. The program provides strong evidence to the public that the program works.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA

Program Adaptation: Taking actions that adapt your program to ensure its ongoing effectiveness									
	To little or no extent						To a very great extent		Not able to answer
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7		
1. The program periodically reviews the evidence base.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	
2. The program adapts strategies as needed.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	
3. The program adapts to new science.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	
4. The program proactively adapts to changes in the environment.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	
5. The program makes decisions about which components are ineffective and should not continue.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	

Communications: Strategic communication with stakeholders and the public about your program									
	To little or no extent						To a very great extent		Not able to answer
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7		
1. The program has communication strategies to secure and maintain public support.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	
2. Program staff communicate the need for the program to the public.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	
3. The program is marketed in a way that generates interest.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	
4. The program increases community awareness of the issue.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	
5. The program demonstrates its value to the public.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	

Strategic Planning: Using processes that guide your program's direction, goals, and strategies									
	To little or no extent						To a very great extent		Not able to answer
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7		
1. The program plans for future resource needs.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	
2. The program has a long-term financial plan.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	
3. The program has a sustainability plan.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	
4. The program's goals are understood by all stakeholders.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	
5. The program clearly outlines roles and responsibilities for all stakeholder	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA	

This completes the questionnaire.
Thank you.

15 FIGURES

Figure 1: Overall flow-chart of the implementation study

16 TABLES

Table 1: Description of the implementation centres for HPV

Name of the company where the pilot study is implemented (acronym in the project)	NACE code	Total number of employees	Principal investigator (PI) for the HPV intervention	Contact email for the PI

Table 2: Prevention and health promotion initiatives in the implementation centres

Name of the company (acronym in the project)	Other preventive program for HPV before the current project			Prevention program for cancer (past or current)			Health promotion program (past or current)		
	Yes	No	Don't know	Yes	No	Don't know	Yes	No	Don't know

Table 3: Resources dedicated to the project in the implementation centres

Name of the company (acronym in the project)	Where will be implemented the pilot intervention				Who will implement the pilot intervention				
	OHS medical office inside the premises	OHS medical office outside the premises	OHS mobile unit	Others	occupational health specialists (Number)	other medical doctors (Number)	occupational health nurses (Number)	laboratory staff (Number)	support staff (IT, statisticians, etc) (Number)

17 UPDATES FOLLOWING THE 1ST PROJECT TECHNICAL REVIEW

Section 14 : Annex 14.1- The Informed consent template has been updated as follows: Do I agree to receive information about the health risks of human papillomavirus (HPV) infection, including the risk of cancer due to chronic infection? I AGREE I DISAGREE „

Indeed, lack of this sentence was an unfortunate omission/typo in Deliverable D4.1. However, unlike the version included in D4.1, the actual informed consent form provided to each study participant contained this statement. Please note that the template included in the deliverable was intended as an example for implementing centers in WP4, and includes also HCV and/or HP, as all implementing centers in WP4 conduct more than one intervention (meaning HPV +HCV and/or HP).

Point 9.1 has a new section, Sample Size Justification, and the section Timeline has been updated. Both sections are in accordance with the CPW Grant Agreement.

CPW is a project funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe – Research and Innovation funding programme (2021 - 2027), under grant agreement (GA 101104716). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.